

Understanding and Mitigating the Ecological Footprint of State Border Barriers

FINAL REPORT TO NAWA—March 2025

Principal Investigator: Katarzyna Nowak (knowak02@gmail.com)

NAWA Team (in alphabetical order): Jakub Bubnicki, Bogdan Jaroszewicz, Ewa Komar, Łukasz Kuberski, Paweł Nowak, Ireneusz Ruczyński, Marcin Zegarek, Michał Żmihorski

International Partners: Elena Bužan, Zdenka Křenová, Boštjan Pokorny, Hubert Potočnik, Nuria Selva, Myles Traphagen

Additional contributors: Wojciech Adamowski, Beata Bramorska, Marta Kołodziej-Sobocińska, Lucyna Marciniak, Marcin Mazurkiewicz, Rosanne Michielsen, Kamil Morawski, Shane A. Richards, Tomasz Samojlik, Ireneusz Smerczyński, Michał Śmielak, Izabela Stachowicz, Justyna Wiśniewska, Aleksandra Wróbel, Milena Zduniak

Permissions: Regional Directors for Environmental Protection and Białowieża National Park

Urgency grant from Polish National Agency for Academic Exchange (NAWA),
Grant/Award Number BPN/GIN/2023/1/00007/U/0001

Executive Summary

The hardening of international borders through fortification and militarization is on the rise around the world. Construction of border infrastructure often proceeds without environmental review or input from ecologists. As a result, natural areas of biological importance are often degraded through a combination of habitat fragmentation, disruption of ecosystem functions, blockage of animal movements, propagation of invasive species, and a suite of other effects. This project focused on the section of the Poland-Belarus border that runs along Białowieża Forest, a Natura 2000 and UNESCO World Heritage site. The project ran for 18 months beginning in August 2023. Our overarching research aim was to improve understanding of the ecological effects of the fortified border on the forest (e.g., heat, light, noise), ramifications for wild animals (e.g., activity, movement including crossing of barriers, human-wildlife interactions) and plants (e.g., alien and invasive species) to help inform further monitoring and potential mitigation.

We employed a combination of methods aimed at gauging the ecological effects of border fortification and militarization including 1) **transects**, to investigate animal activity near the border by enumerating animal dung piles and other signs as well as register human signs; 2) **camera traps**, for detection of wildlife and people in the vicinity of the border to further understand the relationship if any between human and wildlife presence and activity; 3) **sampling of sound with audio moths and song meters** to describe the border soundscape with a focus on anthrophony; 4) **plant surveys** to gain baseline data on thermophilic, non-forest, pioneer, non-native and invasive plant species along the border; 5) **temperature and light measurements** to estimate extent of edge effects; and 6) **snow-tracking** along the border to know which species approach the border and cross barriers. With the exception of plant transects and snow-tracking, the above methods were conducted both along the border and also along at least one road in Białowieża Forest as a type of “control” or frame of reference. Further to this field program, to improve our wider understanding of state border barrier effects and mitigation, we **exchanged knowledge with international colleagues** from the United States, Czech Republic, Slovenia and Spain. These colleagues visited Białowieża to share knowledge, join in fieldwork, compare their border regions with ours, and jointly consider potential research approaches and conservation solutions in borderlands.

In our study sites in Białowieża Forest, we found higher human presence along the border than control roads on the basis of both transect and camera trap data. On transects, we found fewer wildlife signs along the edge of both the border and roads suggesting animal avoidance; the effect was stronger along the border than control roads. On transects, plastic pollution was the dominant human sign. We also recorded other human signs including building materials, campfires, as well as cut and toppled trees with the highest number recorded in the strict reserve of Białowieża National Park (~100 trees in a 200m-long transect). Camera trap capture rates varied by taxon; generally, humans were more frequently captured on cameras than wildlife, especially at border sites. Wolves seemed to frequent the border edge up to 250m, while ungulates tended to be captured at intermediate distances from both the border and

roads. Mesocarnivores were fairly evenly captured on cameras but snow-tracking yielded further insights.

On the basis of snow-tracking, we found evidence (in winter 2024) that small mammals and mesocarnivores were able to cross the secondary barriers (forest net and concertina) and possibly also the main barrier and that domestic carnivores and mesocarnivores are attracted to the border for feeding opportunities at military outposts (next to which we observed a variety of discarded food and food packaging) thereby altering the human-wildlife-domestic animal interface. Soldiers reported foxes, marten, domestic cats and other animals “visiting” them at outposts both in winter 2024 and as recently as January 2025, when we repeated transects for a third time in some areas and also carried out limited snow-tracking.

The soundscape was sampled in two independent ways: continuous recording on a large spatial scale for one week in winter 2024 (prior to the onset of bird spring vocal activity) and long-term sampling over several (8) months in spring to autumn/winter in the strict reserve of Białowieża National Park. Sounds were classed into three categories: anthrophony (human voices, vehicles, music, barking dogs, gunshots), biophony (owls, woodpeckers) and geophony (wind). We detected some anthropogenic sounds (e.g., helicopters, gunshots) penetrating well into the forest interior but overall, anthrophony appeared to penetrate 100-250m into the forest interior.

Further to the anthrophony, on the basis of the song meter recordings, we found some preliminary evidence that the bird community at the state border edge differs from the bird community 250m and 500m into the forest interior (the two forest interior communities differed to a substantial lesser extent from each other than either did from the border edge). This early finding warrants further study. Overall, the border situation has been dynamic with quiet periods interspersed with more noisy, characterized by building, patrolling, and exclusion zones. This means that sound samples collected to date were not fully representative of this spectrum.

In autumn 2024, we recorded 130 plants species in 4.8km of transects along the border including 13 with invasion potential including *Conyza canadensis*, *Solidago canadensis* and *Bidens frondosa*. These species are benefiting from the secondary barriers where browsing by ungulates is excluded. We also sampled an additional 4.8km inside the forest 50m away from the border; 23% of the plant taxa recorded along the border was also recorded 50m into the forest interior and, of these, three were invasive. As expected, temperature was highest at the edge with an up to 1 degree Celsius difference between the edge and 100 m into the forest. This elevated temperature at the edge likely contributes to the growth of thermophilic plants along the border such as *Lathyrus silvestris*, *Clinopodium vulgare*, *Astragalus glycyphyllos*, *Vicia* spp., and *Trifolium* spp.

Of research methods employed, with respect to wildlife responses to the border fortification and militarization, snow-tracking, though relatively limited, yielded key insights into which species are crossing barriers. Snow-tracking also informed us about which species are aggregating around military outposts along the border for feeding opportunities. Transects yielded data on plastic pollution and possible accumulation of deer sign at intermediate distances from the edge

suggesting a possible risk response distance. Camera traps provided data on presence of species when no sign is left or when sign is difficult to detect on transects such as for large carnivores and mesocarnivores; they also provided information on precise time and location as well as weather conditions (as cameras also record temperature) and may offer insights into animal behavior for example more nocturnal activity when near the border relative to when near roads. Camera traps also provide information on human presence when no obvious sign is left or can be detected.

Further to these field methods, through *ad hoc* conversations with soldiers, we gained insights into which species they are seeing, which species are successfully crossing the main barrier (e.g., red fox), which animals (e.g., domestic cats) are coming through the barrier from the BY side, and finally that bison approach the barrier from the Belarusian side in at least two locations (our northernmost study site north of Stare Masiewo and a site near Białowieża south of Browska Road) suggesting either that some bison are still stuck in the habitat pockets between our border and the Belarusian sistema or that there's bison movement through possibly gaps in the sistema.

Monitoring recommendations include: Monitor on an ongoing basis; appreciate what type of insight each kind of method can bring; possibly consider other, additional methods such as a telemetry study of species known to cross the barriers (e.g., red foxes), survey of soldiers stationed at the border about their wildlife sightings including of animals approaching the barrier from the other side, sightings of wildlife crossing the barriers, and human-wildlife interactions including at outposts. Additional camera trapping in particular if cameras are permitted to face the barriers could yield valuable information and, eventually, help shape recommendations for additional gate placement and measure of efficacy of conservation interventions including gates.

Gates in the barrier remained closed throughout our study period and it is suggested that the conditions and circumstances required to open these or create new ones are considered ideally in some communication with the Belarusian side (via a third party such as UNESCO or IUCN) where the sistema might be opened simultaneously to restore and enable wildlife movement. This might be done in the vicinity of an important resource where animals are needing access such as streams, rivers or waterholes (several including extensive waterholes were noted on transects and surveys). Given drought conditions, water and access to it will become more important as the climate continues to warm. Restricting wildlife movements could also result in negative interactions between people and large mammals if species of large carnivores and herbivores shift westward into relatively more human-dense areas. As such, conservation solutions must be pursued. This forest has endured past human conflicts and we must ensure that it endures this period.

*Lead writer of this report was Katarzyna Nowak; errors are her own
Photos in the report were taken by Katarzyna Nowak unless otherwise credited*

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
Table of Contents	4
Acronyms and Abbreviations	5
Glossary of Terms	5
Preface / Introduction	6
Gantt of Project Activities	8
Study Area: Białowieża Forest	9
Meeting and Knowledge Exchange with International Partners	10
Pilot: Transects, Camera Traps, Audio Moths	13
1) Transects-pilot	14
2) Camera traps-pilot	15
3) Sound-pilot	15
Study Locations—13 study sites	15
Camera Trapping—12 sites with 3 cameras in each	17
Transects—13 sites with 6 transects in each	29
Snow-Tracking—along the state border	32
Forest Soundscape Survey	38
Soundscape at varying distances from state border edge	38
Long-term forest soundscape monitoring	42
Temperature—4 sites, 2 at border, 2 at road	47
Plant Transects—along the state border	52
Important Resources Near the Border	60
Summary of Results	61
Threat Overview	62
Recommendations	64
Changes to initial plans including from unanticipated challenges	68
Conference presentations	69
Additional outputs	69
Publications	69
Reports	70
Media engagements	70
References	71
Appendices	75

Acronyms and Abbreviations

BF	Białowieża Forest
BNP	Białowieża National Park
BSG	Białowieża Geobotanical Station
MRIPAS	Mammal Research Institute Polish Academy of Sciences
PL-BY	Poland-Belarus, used to refer to the border
RDOŚ	Generalna Dyrekcja Ochrony Środowiska / Regional Directorate for Environmental Protection
TBA	Transboundary Natural Areas
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
US-MX	United States-Mexico, used to refer to the border

Glossary of Terms

Edge effects: altered conditions in, for example, microclimate associated with abrupt transition in habitats or communities at the boundary at which they meet. While there are positive and negative edge effects, the term is generally now used to refer to ecological deterioration associated with anthropogenic disturbance. In forests, human-induced edges will often be sharp rather than gradual, have high solar radiation, wind disturbance, low humidity and support thermophilic plants; such edges can exacerbate wildfires, tree mortality, human-wildlife conflicts and propagation of invasive species.

Encounter rate: how often a target of interest is detected along a specified distance. This is distinct from camera trap rate which refers to how often a camera records a species.

Mesocarnivore: collective name for mammalian carnivores that have small to medium body size, smaller range sizes and more omnivorous/less carnivorous diets relative to large carnivores.

Militarization: process of increasing and organizing military activities possibly for prevention of or preparation for conflict. In the case of border militarization, this involves defense often in the form of barriers and other tactical infrastructure.

One Health: the close interconnectedness of animal, human and environmental health.

Soundscape: collection of sounds in a given space or landscape; the acoustic environment.

Transect: a path or line, often straight, along which observations are recorded and measurements are made. While the length of the line is often pre-determined, the width is calculated on the basis of sighting distance from the line. In “Distance sampling” a detection function will model the probability of detecting an animal or sign (e.g., dung pile) on the basis of distance from the line and help estimate density or abundance of organisms in a given area.

Preface / Introduction

Only 11% of terrestrial borderlands enjoy some form of nature protection on both sides of a shared border (Zhang et al. 2025). Meanwhile, transboundary natural areas (TBAs)—often high in biodiversity—are under increasing pressure on account of geopolitical tensions and defensive border security measures (Wade 2017; Peters et al. 2018; Sennett & Chambers 2025). TBAs are therefore of conservation priority if ecological networks and biodiversity are to be maintained or restored (Liu et al. 2020; Cazzolla Gatti 2024). Removing fences and other barriers to facilitate animal movement and improve connectivity and integrity of natural ecosystems remains an explicit part of national biodiversity strategies and action plans in the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework (LLC 2024). In Europe, as part of the European Union Biodiversity Strategy 2030, member states committed to designing a Trans-European Nature Network (TEN-N) (http://www.carpathianconvention.org/projects_naturaconnect/). The goal of TEN-N is to ensure connectivity between natural environments, their component parts and ecological functions. Meanwhile, we are still (and until 2030) in the UN Decade of Restoration with the aim to “prevent, halt and reverse the degradation of ecosystems on every continent and in every ocean.”

International political boundaries challenge these conservation and restoration goals (Thornton et al. 2017) largely on account of border militarization and fortification in TBAs. Connectivity threats at political borders also hinder climate change adaptation (Titley et al. 2021). Poland is no exception (Jaroszewicz et al. 2021; Nowak et al. 2023; Błaszczyk et al. 2024); a 5.5 meter high state border barrier was constructed along the Polish-Belarusian border in 2022 with additional border fortification added since then. The border remains militarized and further land degradation justified on the basis of national security is underway, for example cutting of trees and vegetation along roads and rivers (Wajrak 2024), clearing of old abandoned forest roads (UNESCO 2024), modification or expansion of infrastructure in natural areas including a plan to upgrade the border road possibly with the use of asphalt.

The impact on animal movement and distribution is already becoming quite apparent (Schmidt et al. 2024). From the Polish Border Guard’s own video footage, there exist examples from 2014 showing a herd of wild boar crossing the Polish-Belarusian border (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JmEH7kjyec0&list=PPSV>) in contrast with a video from 2022 demonstrating a lack of crossing potential for species such as roe deer and wolf (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q7IScsqjnGg&list=PPSV>) (Fig. 1 show stills from these two videos). Other impacts, such as roadkill and roadside tree damages, may occur in excess of five kilometers from the border; therefore, the footprint of border militarization and fortification is far wider than the 15 meter border strip (Nowak et al. under review).

More than half of the 418 km PL-BY border is Natura 2000 adjacent (Fig. 2). One of these Natura 2000 sites (~30% of the section of border with a barrier) is Białowieża Forest, a transboundary World Heritage site listed by UNESCO in 1992. According to Brocada and Piana (2022), “The case of Białowieża suggests the potential of a new field of investigation on the militarization of natural, protected areas in Europe as well as around the world”.

Zwierzęta na granicy
 Straż Graniczna
 2.6K views · Jan 22, 2014
 Dzięki możliwościom naszych urządzeń, takich jak np. popląsły obserwacyjny, udaje nam się uchwycić na pastwie drogi granicznej także widoki, jak na zdjęciach i filmie
 Wszystkie zdjęcia wykonano na odcinku granicy polsko-białoruskiej, ochranianym przez placówkę w Kuzhniy. Show more

Oddanie kolejnego odcinka bariery elektronicznej
 Straż Graniczna
 4.6K views · Dec 29, 2022
 Oddany do użytku 29 grudnia odcinek bariery elektronicznej na długość 17,6 km i działo na odcinkach ochranianych przez placówki SG w Nowym Dworcu i Lipuku. Obecnie bariera elektroniczna ma 72 km.

Fig. 1 Stills from border guard videos from 2014 of wild boar crossing the PL-BY border (left) and from 2022 of roe deer halting at the border road and barrier (right)—shows contrast in animal movement behavior at this border in a <10 yr period.

Access to such videos for example from the electronic barrier (installed in recent years) would enable more in-depth analysis of wildlife interactions with the border and barriers.

Fig. 2 Natura 2000 sites along the 418 km Polish-Belarusian border.

In addition to the usual anticipated effects of border fortification and militarization such as blockage of animal movements (Harrity et al. 2024; Lei & Wang 2025) and displacement of animals by human activities (McCallum et al. 2014) there also exist unanticipated consequences such as high energetic expenditure associated with searching for gaps in fences to access essential resources (Chambers et al. 2022), or to disperse; habituation to people of, especially, opportunistic species like red foxes and marten (pers. obs., 2024); roadkill and roadside tree damages on account of heavier vehicle traffic along forest roads (Nowak et al. under review); difficulties conducting research, monitoring and biodiversity inventories (Edwards et al. 2020, Selva et al. in press); and also disconnect between local people and nature in transboundary ecosystems on account of presence of uniformed services, heavy machinery and access restrictions (Nowak et al. 2024).

An urgency grant from the Polish National Agency for Academic Exchange (NAWA) enabled us to learn from researchers working in other border regions, and to begin to collect data which we hope can improve understanding of the ecological effects of border fortification in Białowieża Forest, to inform a longer-term monitoring program, planning of mitigation measures, and eventual re-connection of the landscapes on this border. In addition, our work might serve as a forewarning to researchers working in other border regions to collect baseline data and not take transboundary connectivity and cooperation for granted. Our main project activities are shown in Fig. 3.

Gantt of Project Activities

Main project activities are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Gantt chart showing project activities starting from in-person meetings with partners in 08-2023 until final fieldwork in Białowieża Forest in 02-2025.

Study Area: Białowieża Forest

Białowieża Forest is an exceptional remnant of ancient lowland forest which has retained ecological features and processes for some 12,000 years (Jaroszewicz et al. 2019). Białowieża Forest, a Natura 2000 and UNESCO World Heritage site, meets the international border for 53,416 m (53.4 km). The forest along the border is managed primarily by three authorities (Fig.4, Table 1), State Forests (44.3%), Regional Directorate for Environmental Protection (34.3%) responsible for nature reserves, and Białowieża National Park (18.5%) in charge of the national park including the strict reserve. The remaining ~3% is managed by other entities (glade in the village of Stare Masiewo and border crossing at Królewska Road). Given the linear nature of the border infrastructure, and vehicle and foot traffic along the border road, this shared jurisdiction of forest along the border means that management activities or lack thereof in one area are bound to impact others. Interventions and mitigation measures must therefore ideally be harmonized. Such considerations of course need to extend beyond the protected areas and to the transborder sphere, in as much as is currently possible, and in lieu of eventual restoration of connectivity.

Fig. 4 The state border runs alongside Białowieża Forest for 53.4 km. Three main authorities manage the forest along the border: State Forests, RDOŚ, and BPN.

The border strip itself (15 meters) falls outside of the jurisdiction of these authorities.

Table 1. Authorities with jurisdiction in Białowieża Forest along the state border.

Authority (acronym in Polish)	Length along state border (m)	Białowieża NP buffer zone
Białowieża National Park (BPN)	9,861	-
Regional Directorate for Environmental Protection (RDOŚ)	18,324	1,009
State Forests (LP)	23,635	5,636
Other	1,596	-
Total	53,416	6,645

Meeting and Knowledge Exchange with International Partners

Our meeting with international partners, working in other border regions, convened in late August to September 2023 in Białowieża. Slovenian and Czech partners arrived in late August and, during their visit, an open hybrid seminar was co-organized and hosted by Mammal Research Institute Polish Academy of Sciences (MRIPAS) on 1 September (Fig. 5). Our U.S. partner contributed to this seminar online. We also held field visits in the days prior and convened a workshop the following day during which we exchanged information about a variety of aspects about our respective border regions; the information from this workshop is compiled into a table in Appendix 1 of this report. Our U.S. partner later arrived and stayed for several weeks in September 2023; he gave an in-person open seminar at MRIPAS. He also donated six camera traps which we set up together in the field as part of our pilot.

Our Spanish partner visited toward the end of the project, in January 2025, to assist with this final project report, final round of transects, and to attend a meeting in the region on the topic of “nature in crisis” organized by the research group *Badaczki i Badacze na Granicy* (Researchers on the Border; <https://www.bbng.org/>) at which we shared some of our project results and considered ways in which the humanitarian crisis intersects with environmental aspects.

Socio-ecological effects of state border barriers

Conference Hall & Online

Friday 1 September

9:45 AM CET

Prof. Boštjan Pokorny

„Recent situation and wildlife (ungulate) mortality in border fences in south-eastern Europe: case studies along Slovenia-Croatia and Hungary-Croatia border”

Assist. Prof. Hubert Potočník

„Potential and actual impact of Slovenia-Croatia border fences on habitat connectivity for bears, wolves and lynx”

Prof. Elena Bužan

„Assessing paternity and spatial genetic structure to uncover anthropogenic barriers in the environment”

Dr Zdenka Křenová

„Long-term effects of the Iron Curtain era: Šumava”

Myles Traphagen

„The US-Mexico border wall experience and the importance of measuring and monitoring”

Dr Katarzyna Nowak

„Footprint of Poland’s border barrier extends beyond the border: Data from a forest road in Białowieża Forest”

Prof. Bogdan Jaroszewicz

„Effects of state border policies on people’s interactions with and perceptions of Białowieża Forest”

Fig. 5 Seminar poster, designed by Beata Bramorska (MRIPAS).

In terms of shared outputs with our international partners, since the initiation of the project, we have published one essay together with our U.S. colleague about threats to conservation posed by national security interests (Nowak et al. 2023). We also worked on a graphic together with a collaborator from MRIPAS to compare and contrast our border situations (Fig. 6). We wrote a book chapter with our Spanish colleague (Selva et al. in press) about wildlife research in human conflict-affected areas (including Białowieża Forest as a case study) for an edited volume about war and the environment. We wrote an article with our Czech colleague (Křenová and Nowak 2025) for *Šumava Journal* on the 35th anniversary of the fall of the Iron Curtain era. We have shared our project findings at several conferences (see section towards end of this report on conference presentations) and plan to share our findings in May 2025 at the 14th European Vertebrate Management Conference in Slovenia organized by our lead Slovenian partner. While we have yet to realize our original plan of preparing a guide for researchers working in other borderlands, some such guidelines are already embodied in the above-mentioned outputs to date.

Fig. 6 We found one potential effective way of communicating our findings would be through the use of a graphic summarizing the various effects of border barriers akin to graphics of cumulative effects made in places like British Columbia (www2.gov.bc.ca) where various anthropogenic uses of a landscape combine with natural changes historically, presently, and into the future. We therefore took our inspiration from this approach and, working with illustrator-scientist Tomasz Samojlik (MRIPAS), created images of the border situations in PL-BY and US-MX. As the graphic shows, some effects such as blockage of animals' free movement and leftover construction materials are common, others such as cutting of trees and saguaro cacti are similar, and still others, for example artificial lighting at the US-MX border and roadside tree damages along forest roads near the PL-BY border may be site-specific.

Illustrations by Tomasz Samojlik

Pilot: Transects, Camera Traps, Audio Moths—fine-tuning methods and selection of focal sites

We deployed six camera traps as part of our pilot in two locations along the border at three distances from the border: “at” the border (approximately 15 meters into the forest from the border road), at 250m and 500m from the border. The cameras were oriented 180 degrees from the border facing into the forest to prevent objections from authorities. This differs from the camera set up used by our colleagues at the US-MX border, where cameras face the barrier and therefore inform researchers about species that are able or unable to cross the main barrier. On the basis of their research, 86% of wildlife movements are impeded with only 9% of interactions by wildlife with the infrastructure on the US-MX border resulting in successful crossings (their recently published work on this subject can be found here: [Harrity et al. 2024](#)). We were not able to estimate this and the best information we have to date on crossing potential comes from previous telemetry work by MRIPAS, snow-tracking we carried out in winter 2024 and winter 2025, and *ad hoc* communications with military personnel stationed on the border and reporting wildlife sightings and crossings.

Also in September, we began transect work initially walking three 500-meter long transects parallel to the border at the edge, 250m and 500m (consistent with camera trap arrays); we continued transects into October adding a different transect design, namely shorter 200-meter long transects at additional distances from the border. We also piloted acoustic devices in October in the areas of our camera traps and the wider area.

We identified 16 potential study sites along the border and 6 along roads (intended to provide a frame of reference, if not a “control”) (Fig. 7) with the ultimate aim being to select 9-10 sites along the border and 3-5 sites along roads for 2024 fieldwork pending permissions to conduct research in the national park and nature reserves.

We held two planning sessions, in MRIPAS and at BSG, in autumn 2023 during which pilot data were shared and design of transects, camera trap and audio sampling were discussed. Further details are below, organized by each respective method.

Fig. 7 Potential sites (16 along the border and 6 along roads) were identified and a subset of these (6 along the border, 3 along roads) were pilot sampled in autumn 2023.

1) Transects-pilot

Six sites were transect-sampled along the border using the following configurations:

- 3 areas with 3 500-m long transects at 3 distances from the border: at the border, 250m and 500m
- 3 areas with 5 200-m long transects at 5 distances from the border: at the border, 50m, 100m, 250m, and 500m

Three sites were transect-sampled along roads:

- 3 areas with 3 500-m long transects at 3 distances from the edge: along road, 250m and 500m from road edge

We attempted to pilot these different sampling protocols to gauge how much time these variations take and what differences we might see at varying distances from the border and road edges. Given the effort required to walk 500-meter long transects and to balance this effort with the number of transects walked, it was decided that 200-meter transect lengths would be a compromise and that we would add a sixth distance of 150m from the border/road edge to better detect a gradient. It was therefore decided to have 6 200-meter long transects: at the edge (of the state border and roads), and at 50m, 100m, 150m, 250m, and 500m from the edge.

2) Camera traps-pilot

Six cameras were installed in two areas along the border at three distances: 15m, 250m and 500m from the edge. These successfully captured a variety of species. It was decided that we would maintain this configuration going forward to maximize the number of sites sampled along the border. We would also select at least a third of the number of sites along roads for comparison/a frame of reference.

3) Sound-pilot

A pilot study was conducted in October 2023 to refine the methodology and sampling scheme for a larger-scale sound recording study planned for winter 2024. The pilot aimed to determine appropriate sampling distances from the border, assess the propagation of anthropogenic sounds in the forest, and evaluate the performance of recording devices at low temperatures. Detector performance in low temperatures had to be tested, as the recorders intended for the border soundscape study had not previously been used in autumn-winter conditions; also, battery life under extended operation in cold environments had to be verified.

Methods

Nine recording points distributed across different spatial contexts were selected: three along a forest road (Browska Road), three near the border, and three along a transect perpendicular to the border, in the forest interior, at increasing distances of 200m, 500m, and 2000m.

Recordings were conducted using a sample rate of 32 kHz, with medium gain settings and a recording duration of 3600 seconds per session. A band-pass filter (0.7 kHz - 16.0 kHz) was applied to minimize microphone self-noise below 700 Hz, as frequencies below this threshold primarily captured background noise rather than relevant environmental sounds.

Key conclusions

Based on the pilot study, it was determined that:

- The sampling distance should extend to at least 250 m into the forest.
- The first measurement point should be placed as close to the barrier as possible.
- At low temperatures, the recorders will operate for at least five days.

Based on the pilot observations, the acoustic study design was readied for the winter period.

Study Locations—13 study sites

We selected sites on the basis of 1) forest type, namely pine-spruce and oak-hornbeam; however, despite careful site selection we did still have alder bog stands in parts of several of our study areas; 2) relatively reasonable access by vehicle, bicycle and/or on foot; 3) sample coverage from north to south; 4) coverage roughly proportional to the types of forest management found along the border (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8 Selected sites included 9 along the border and 3 along roads. An additional 10th site was sampled along the border with the use of transects and audio moths but we did not have sufficient camera traps to also camera trap this site (not shown but was below the road site nearest the border just north of Kamieniecka Road).

Border sites included six on State Forest land (in five of these, cameras were set); two sites in Nature Reserves (we initially planned for 3 sites however we opted against sampling in Kozłowe Borki because of various challenges, both wet terrain and intensity of military activity associated with people crossing the border); and two sites in BPN (1 in strict reserve, 1 outside of strict reserve).

Road sites included 2 sites along Zwierzyniecka Road (one in north, one in south) and one site along Kamieniecka Road. Criteria for road sites included that they run at least roughly N-S like most of the border and that the road is approximately similar in width to the border road. Sampling configuration is shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 9 Configuration of transects (6 transects), cameras (3 camera traps), sound sampling (3-4 devices), snow tracking (only along border), and plant surveys (only along border), up to 500m from the border and road edge.

Camera Trapping—12 sites with 3 cameras in each

We deployed 36 cameras starting with pilot cameras in September 2023, finalizing the entire camera trap set up on 9 Feb. 2024, and removing the last cameras/finishing the camera trap sampling effort on 2 December 2024; some cameras therefore ran for more than 1 year.

While all cameras were in the forest, at several locations (which we selected on the basis of criteria discussed above about site selection) they were near enough to a road to pick up motorized traffic (in some places quads, not vehicles). We discussed moving cameras (and audio in fact) further away from any roads; however, it is our experience that BF is criss-crossed by forest roads to such an extent that, especially in State Forests, it is hard to walk 0.5 km

without hitting a forest road. It was therefore more not less representative to leave things as they were although in future analysis, the shortest straight line distances of cameras to forest roads, buildings, forestry enclosures, and other anthropogenic features may be calculated and included in modelling as it may help explain human presence/anthropogenic pressure and wildlife trap rates at these locations. As described above, cameras faced away from the border barrier and, for consistency, away from roads and into the forest (Fig. 10).

The total sampling effort for the camera trapping portion of the study amounted to 9,423 camera trap days, distributed across two treatments/edge types: border (7,466 camera days) and road (1,957 camera days). Sampling ran from September 2023 to December 2024, with a total of 192 camera deployments (~50 camera trap days each). Of these, 156 deployments were associated with the border and 37 with the road, covering 36 unique locations—27 along the border and 9 along the road. A sample of photographs from the border edge are shown in Figure 11.

Fig. 10 Camera traps had to face away from the border barrier, into the forest.

Fig. 11 Sample of photographs from state border edge camera traps: roe and red deer, wolf and red fox, moose and bison, and domestic dog; note their varied orientation: towards (roe deer, red fox, domestic dog), along (red deer, wolf) and from (dog) the border. The bison photo (from north of Stare Masiewo) is from the only site from among our border sample sites where we recorded bison near the state border edge (from photos and dung transects); it is also one of two sites where soldiers reported bison approaching the barrier from the other (BY) side.

 18 C 29.42 inHg GB2M0 06/27/2024 06:14AM

 17 C 29.13 inHg GD4M0 07/03/2024 11:29AM

17 C 29.38 inHg

GB1M0

07/14/2024 08:02AM

19 C 29.25 inHg

GN3M0

07/24/2024 09:24PM

All camera trap data was organized in the open-source TRAPPER system (<https://gitlab.com/trapper-project>), which allows for efficient management of large collections of multimedia data and camera trap metadata in an automated way, using AI algorithms to classify the contents of images and videos, and is compliant with the global camera trap data description and exchange standard Camtrap DP (<https://tdwg.github.io/camtrap-dp>). In the first step, all photos were automatically classified

using the Megadetector v5a (<https://github.com/microsoft/CameraTraps>; Beery et al. 2019) AI model for animal detection. The result was a classification of images into those containing animals, people, vehicles, or empty frames. Next, the images containing animals were classified to species-level using the Trapper AI v02-2024 model (<https://huggingface.co/OSCF/TrapperAI-v02.2024>). Both models are fully integrated with the TRAPPER AI system. Finally, to generate high-quality monitoring data, all photos were subjected to additional expert (human) verification of the species identified by the model, as well as determination of the number of individuals observed (group size) and, for some species, their sex and age.

The analyzed dataset contained a total of 23,381 images of species captured by the camera traps. The total number of independent observations (independent events) of animal (non-human) species reached 3995, and 594 for human observations (excluding all footage during camera installation and dismantling). Aggregating observations from the level of individual images into independent events is a necessary step preceding most ecological statistical analyses. Its purpose is to avoid the serious problem of pseudo-replication of observed events. Because individuals of wild species, in the vast majority of cases, are not individually identifiable, a minimum time interval of 5 minutes was assumed between consecutive observations. Observations recorded less than 5 minutes apart from the previous one were automatically grouped into sequences corresponding to a single independent observation, for which the number of individuals was determined taking into account the context of the entire sequence.

Overall, camera trap rates were higher for people than animals. For animals, trap rates were higher in autumn than in spring and summer (with no significant difference between autumn and winter), and appear to increase with distance from roads but not necessarily with distance from the border (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12 A-B Trap rate of animals and people (vehicles shown separately) by distance from edge (m) and faceted by edge type (border, road) (A) and trap rate of different functional groups (ungulates, mesocarnivores, humans, etc) by distance from edge and faceted by edge type with vehicles not included (B). Humans were the dominant species captured by cameras, followed by ungulates (more at road sites), and mesocarnivores (more at border sites).

We categorized taxa into groups and tested if counts of humans, large carnivores, mesocarnivores and ungulates vary by edge type and distance from the edge. We used mixed models with negative binomial distribution, as implemented in the R package glmmTMB, R version 4.4.2 (2024-10-31) (R Core Team 2024), because of how our count data were distributed (mean= 1.68, variance= 43.67), i.e. showing a relatively high level of overdispersion. Our response variable was the count of each taxon at each camera trap deployment corrected for sampling effort (i.e. camera trap days) resulting in a daily trapping rate estimated for each taxon and sampling unit (deployment). We included edge type (border or road) and distance from the edge as fixed effects. We included location ID as a random effect to account for repeated measures at the same location. Predicted counts by edge type and distance are visualized in Fig. 13. Ungulates have higher predicted counts at 250-500m from the road and relatively lower counts at the border than road sites; they are more frequently captured compared with carnivores. Humans appear to be more frequently captured at the border than at the road edge. Mesocarnivores, while generally evenly distributed, are predicted more at border sites.

Fig. 13 Predicted counts by edge type and distance from edge for humans, large carnivores, mesocarnivores and ungulates. Warmer/red or yellow = higher predicted count whereas cooler/purple or black = lower predicted count.

We proceeded to model counts of taxa separately using season, edge type, and distance from edge as predictors, and location as random variable, for example:

```
model_wolf_nb <- glmmTMB(count ~ season + edge_type * distance_from_edge_m +
offset(days) + (1 | locationID), family = nbinom2, data = ct_wolf)
```

For moose and bison, we removed the interaction between edge type and distance from edge to run a simplified model (Fig. 14).

Fig. 14 Interaction effects of edge type (border vs road) and distance from edge (0m, 250m, 500m) on different taxa (for moose and bison effects of edge type and distance from edge were tested without interaction). Bright yellow color represents stronger effect sizes; in other words, indicates more of that taxon in that given location.

Humans were most ubiquitous at the border and their presence while higher at the edge (“0” distance) is not strongly dependent on distance (Fig. 14). Red deer seem to be found at intermediate distances (250m) from the border and road while roe deer at the edge of the border and intermediate distance from roads. Wolves appear to be relatively more captured from 0-250m from the border. Possibly, wolves are following prey species to the border or are patrolling what may be the new edge of their territory. A mixed pattern for bison and moose is observed with the former generally more present at roads and latter more at border and, seemingly, with bison possibly more edge-avoidant than moose. Foxes seem relatively constant across both edge types and distances.

Accumulated trap rates of humans, bison, wolves and roe deer are presented in Fig. 15.

Fig. 15 Accumulated camera trap rate by location for four detected species: humans, bison, wolves, and roe deer.

Border disturbance causes shift to nocturnality

Fig. 16 Shifts to nocturnality detected in some taxa when in the vicinity of the border (“granica”) compared with the road (“droga”).

Some of the species such as red fox *Vulpes vulpes*, European badger *Meles meles* and red deer *Cervus elaphus* exhibit a slight shift of activity to nocturnal in the vicinity of the border (Fig. 16). Of these species, the badger exhibits the most significant differences between the border and road. It has the lowest activity overlap ($D_{\text{hat}} = 0.5057$), indicating a major shift in activity patterns between road and border ($p < 0.0001$) and significantly different activity levels ($p = 0.0131$), showing variation in activity intensity. Red deer show higher levels of activity during nights ($p < 0.001$) but maintain similar activity levels. Red fox shows moderate differences, with similar activity patterns but differing levels of activity on the border being higher at night. *Capreolus capreolus* (roe deer) shows the least difference, as both activity overlap and levels are very similar between the two edge types.

Aspects to explore further include seasonal and temporal effects. The camera trapping period was characterized/punctuated by the following events:

- 1) December 2023: addition of secondary barriers in the form of a forest net and concertina along the border road which excluded animals from the immediate border strip;
- 2) Exclusion zones (200-m wide exclusion zone that began 13 June 2024);
- 3) Between August 2024–November 2024: additional fortification of the border associated with construction and noise.

While exclusion zones could in theory be beneficial (Lawrence et al. 2015), in the case of BF, exclusion zones were also instituted in order to carry out further building or fortification activities (see section on sound and anthrophony below) so it is unlikely that these offered reprieve to wildlife.

The Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx*)—a species that is rare in BF (10-15 individuals) and of highest concern in terms of blockage of gene flow by the border barriers—was detected only two times on our cameras. One detection was 500m from one of our control roads, and the other detection was 250m from the state border in a nature reserve in an area where there is no main barrier, only concertina (please see Appendix II for more detail).

Transects—13 sites with 6 transects in each

Transects—for enumerating animal and human signs—were walked initially in September to October 2023 (while we were still experimenting with transect design) and were re-walked in late winter 2024 with some (in State Forests) repeated recently for a third time in early 2025 (2025 data are not yet included in the analysis for this report). In 2024-2025, transects followed the design shown in Fig. 9 which opted for 6 200-m long transects parallel to the infrastructure edge (a design inspired by Jones et al. 2014), or 1.2 km walked in each sample area. Total surveyed in 2023-2024 was 26.1 km (18 km in state border areas, 8.1 km in road areas). In 2025, we sampled in 6 places along the border (7.2 km) and 3 along roads (3.6 km) for an additional 10.8 km sampled with a total of 36.9 km (2023-2025).

Dung has been the main animal sign (in 2023-2024, >1200 dung piles were detected with the vast majority being red and roe deer) followed by animal trails, and signs such as digging, resting, marking or rooting. Trash (>300) was the main human sign with five times as much trash recorded in border than road sites. Other human signs, for example building materials (wires, cement) and recently cut trees (Fig. 17), were second and third respectively to trash and only recorded in the border sites.

Fig. 17 Nearly 100 trees were found cut or uprooted in a 200-m border-adjacent transect in the strict reserve (oddział 320) of BNP and various materials including razor wire, electrical wiring (visible under the spruce in the center of this photo), plastics (bottles, containers, bags) were found.

Wildlife appear to leave the least sign (which may suggest some level of fear or avoidance) at both border and road edges with a stronger avoidance / less sign encountered at the border than road edge (Fig. 18-19B). Human sign was highest at the border edge (Fig. 19A).

Fig. 18 Areas sampled with transects included 3 road sites (bi2, ha1, ha2) and 10 border sites (one area—gb4—was transect-sampled during the pilot stage and in 2025 but we did not have enough cameras to include it in camera-trapping whereas the rest of areas had camera traps).

Fig. 19 A-B Human (A) and animal (B) sign encounter rates per km by edge type and distance from the edge.

Animal sign encounter rates were associated with distance from the infrastructure edge, type of infrastructure (border, road), and year (Fig. 20). That year had an effect may be due to changes in infrastructure such as addition of barriers installed along the border in Dec. 2023 or heavier road use (which might displace wildlife further from an edge), seasonal and/or sampling differences or other factors. The interactions among these factors (edge type, distance from edge, year) remain to be explored further, once our 2025 transect data are added.

Fig. 20 Animal sign per kilometer of transect by edge type, distance from edge and year (with all of these having a positive effect on sign counts), modeled with a generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (family poisson).

If ungulate sign encounter rates peak at intermediate distances (~150m), as this may be their risk response distance, may be something to explore further. This could possibly be evaluated further in combination with information on animals' total time spent in front of camera traps at given distances (a kind of giving-up-density) which may indicate extent of risk perceived (i.e. more time in less risky areas).

In addition, the following non-forest, alien and in several cases invasive plant species were detected along transects in Autumn 2023: *Solidago canadensis*, *Conyza canadensis*, *Tussilago farfara*, *Plantago major*, *Lycopersicon esculentum*, *Artemisia vulgaris*, and *Impatiens parviflora*. We decided to expand on this plant list by purposefully sampling plants along the border in Autumn 2024 (see below section on plant surveys).

Snow-Tracking—along the state border

In early 2024 and 2025, we snow-tracked along the border walking alongside the secondary barriers (forest net and concertina, pictured below in Fig. 21). We covered approximately one-third of the border where Białowieża Forest runs alongside the state border. We tracked in 3 teams of 2 persons in 2024 and 1 team in 2025; each team had one relatively more and one less seasoned observer/tracker. The below analysis includes only 2024 data.

Fig. 21 Border barriers in winter; January 2024.

All animal tracks, their direction in relation to barriers, and human signs (mainly outposts) were recorded along 16.9 km tracked in winter 2024 with 252 records made (20% of these were human). We grouped roe and red deer tracks into “ungulates” and red fox, raccoon dog, badger (Fig. 22), marten, ermine, weasel, unidentified mustelids into “mesocarnivores”. Of the 252 records, 50 were human points (military outposts), 141 mesocarnivore tracks, 39 ungulate tracks, and 16 domestic carnivore (cats and dogs) tracks.

We set out to test the null hypothesis that there are no differences across functional groups in how points are distributed across the line “transect” and no difference across taxa in their potential to permeate barriers.

We filtered the data to ensure that all observations had valid geographical coordinates (latitude and longitude) and removed any rows with missing data (3 mesocarnivore records were removed due to inaccurate coordinates).

We then applied Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering to the human points based on spatial proximity as this clustering method is well-suited for linearly arranged data. This allowed us to divide the human points into distinct clusters. We chose the number of clusters ($k = 3$) based on visual inspection of the hierarchical clustering dendrogram.

After the human clusters were established, we calculated the geographical distance between each mesocarnivore and ungulate point to the nearest human point. The Vincenty distance using the geosphere package in R was employed to measure distances on an ellipsoidal Earth model, ensuring an accurate representation of geographical distances in meters.

We initially computed the mean distances of mesocarnivores and ungulates to the nearest human points to compare how close each group was to humans, on average. Mean distance between mesocarnivores and humans was 93 meters, while the mean distance between ungulates and humans was 217 meters.

We then included the domestic carnivores also to validate our findings as we expected the domestic animals to be closest to human points (Fig. 23). During snow-tracking, soldiers told us that cats (and dogs) were visiting them at outposts, from both sides of the border and even at outposts some distance ($>5\text{km}$) from the nearest village.

Fig. 22 Tracks of a badger crossing the secondary barriers, January 2024.

Fig. 23 Histogram of number of observations of domestic carnivores, mesocarnivores and ungulates in relation to distance to humans.

Statistical significance was tested using Kruskal-Wallis test ($\chi^2 = 29.121$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.001$), and a significant difference in distances to humans between the three groups was detected. Pairwise comparisons of distances to humans using Dunn's test (with Bonferroni correction) showed the following (visualized in Fig. 24):

- Domestic carnivores vs. mesocarnivores: No significant difference ($p = 0.106$, ns)
- Domestic carnivores vs. ungulates: Significant difference ($p < 0.001$, ***)
- Mesocarnivores vs. ungulates: Significant difference ($p < 0.001$, **)

Domestic carnivore points were closest to human clusters (outposts, toilets, signs); then mesocarnivores (no statistical difference with domestic carnivores) and lastly ungulates (statistically different from both domestic and mesocarnivores) (Fig. 24).

Fig. 24 Violin plot showing distribution of distances to humans for domestic carnivores, mesocarnivores, and ungulates on the border. The boxplots within the violins represent the interquartile range, with the central line indicating median distance. Statistical significance was tested using Kruskal-Wallis test and pairwise comparisons with Dunn's test (with Bonferroni correction) showing no significant difference ($p = 0.106$, ns) between domestic carnivores and mesocarnivores in distance to humans, and significant differences between domestic carnivores and ungulates ($p < 0.001$, highly significant ***) and between mesocarnivores and ungulates ($p < 0.01$, moderately significant **).

Domestic and mesocarnivore tracks crossed secondary barriers (forest net and concertina) installed on the border in December 2023 while ungulates (roe and red deer) did not cross (Fig. 25).

Fig. 25 Direction of animal tracks in relation to the secondary border barriers (forest net and concertina). "Unknown" indicates unclear direction or roaming in the general area.

Movement "along" the barriers characterized the majority (>50%) of ungulate tracks. This is informative as it suggests that roe and red deer are expending energy (in winter) possibly to find gaps in the fence. "Across" most commonly characterized tracks of small carnivores (foxes, raccoon dogs, marten and other species) (Fig. 25).

From observations made during snow-tracking, we found evidence (human food scraps, food in faeces) of feeding by carnivores near military outposts which likely explains their proximity to humans along the border. At at least one outpost (in Rezerwat Starzyna) there was intentional feeding of animals in that soldiers had constructed a platform feeder behind their outpost on which we observed slices of bread, vegetable and fruit scraps. At other outposts, there was various food waste and containers discarded and strewn in the forest; some containers had visible bite marks.

When assessing border militarization impacts, we need to therefore also pay attention to the smaller-bodied species (common, highly adaptable, often of least conservation concern) as they could be better sentinels of the effects of border militarization than the large, and shy/less opportunistic species (see Marneweck et al. 2022).

Based on our preliminary observations, mesocarnivores come into accidental or intentional contact with soldiers and other uniformed services as well as with domestic animals (military dogs, also cats and dogs attracted to military outposts for feeding opportunities, shelter, human interaction). As such the wild animals face risks such as vehicles, strewn razor wire,

plastic pollution, depredation by dogs. While on the one hand, they may be overcoming barriers, they are exposed to pathogens, becoming habituated to people, and consuming human food. This has consequences for the wider ecosystem in that mesocarnivores can be disease vectors and conflict species (especially if emboldened or habituated).

During recent snow-tracking in 2025 (data not included in the above analysis yet), we counted some 40 crossing points by foxes in ~2km tracked suggesting that for foxes, the barriers are relatively permeable and proximity to people is not posing much of a deterrent (Fig. 26).

Fig. 26 Fox tracks crossing the secondary barriers with tracks leading to the main barrier where uniformed services confirmed that the animal had crossed to the other side. An active outpost and road to access the outpost was nearby.

Snow-tracking proved to be a very informative method in that it revealed what taxa approach the border, cross barriers, and come into interaction with humans. It was limited mainly by the low amount of snowfall in 2024 and 2025.

Forest Soundscape Survey

An ecosystem's soundscape can affect and be affected by people (Pijanowski et al. 2011). Two independent soundscape measurements were conducted in BF: continuous recording on a large spatial scale for one week in winter 2024 (prior to the onset of bird spring vocal activity) and long-term sampling (eight months) in spring to autumn/winter season 2024 in the strict reserve of BNP (analysis of data in this report includes spring to summer). These measurements were made using different types of recording devices and each of these methods is described in further detail below, alongside results and challenges.

Soundscape at varying distances from state border edge

Our goal was to investigate whether there are differences in the soundscape at varying distances from the border.

Field setup

Measurements were made during the winter, from January to February 2024. We specifically chose a period with low bird vocal activity to minimize the contribution of biophonic sounds (such as singing, vocalizations, and sounds related to bird mating), thus allowing a clearer focus on potential anthropogenic noise. Autonomous Recording Units (ARU) from Audio Moth (ver. 1.2.0; firmware 1.7.1) were used, which are affordable, widely available, and allow for simultaneous recording in multiple locations. The detectors (rented from MRIPAS) were deployed at varying distances from the state border and one road (Kamieniecka Road, located several kilometers away from the border infrastructure but leading towards the border). 28 detectors were placed at 6 border sites and one forest road with four devices per site, at distances of 15m, 100m, 250m, and 500m from the infrastructure edge. This setup was consistent with camera trap configuration and transect work. Due to a malfunction of one detector, data was ultimately collected from 27 devices. Four of these transects were the same as during the audio pilot. The detectors recorded continuously with a sampling rate of 32 kHz, the gain was set to medium, and the duration of individual recordings was set to 60 minutes.

Acoustic analyses

ARUs operated continuously 24/7 for 7 days. Prior to analysis, the recordings were cut into 1-minute samples. All analyses were conducted using these 1-minute samples. For all acoustic analyses we used Wildlife Acoustics Kaleidoscope Pro software (version 5.6.8).

Acoustic indices: To characterize the soundscape, we calculated three commonly used acoustic indices (Bradfer-Lawrence et al. 2019):

- 1. Normalized Difference Soundscape Index (NDSI)**

- This index measures the proportion of biophony (e.g., animal vocalizations) to anthropophony (human-generated sounds such as traffic, machinery, or gunshots).

- NDSI ranges from -1 to 1, with values closer to 1 indicating dominance by biological sounds and values closer to -1 suggesting a strong presence of anthropogenic noise.
 - We computed NDSI in the frequency range of 1,000–8,000 Hz, using the following limits:
 - Anthrophony: 500–2,000 Hz
 - Biophony: 2,000–8,000 Hz
 - Because NDSI is particularly sensitive to anthropogenic disturbance, it was our primary index of interest.
2. **Acoustic Diversity Index (ADI)**
- ADI assesses how many different frequency bands are active and the intensity within those bands.
 - Higher ADI values typically reflect greater acoustic diversity.
 - We tested ADI over two frequency ranges: a narrower range of 250–1,500 Hz to capture potential anthropogenic sounds (ADI_low), and a more standard broader range of 250-10,000 Hz to capture overall diversity (ADI).
3. **Acoustic Evenness Index (AEI)**
- AEI quantifies how evenly energy is distributed across various frequency bands.
 - Higher AEI values indicate a more uniform distribution of acoustic energy, which can suggest a complex acoustic environment.
 - We tested AEI over two frequency ranges: a narrower range of 250–1,500 Hz to capture potential anthropogenic sounds (AEI_low), and a more standard broader range of 250-10,000 Hz to capture overall diversity (AEI).

Cluster Classification: We also performed a cluster analysis. Firstly dominant, minimum, and maximum frequencies, as well as linear-scale cepstral coefficients of each sample were estimated; then, groups of samples exhibiting similar acoustic profiles were identified. We defined a frequency range of 100-1000Hz and detection length 1-10 seconds. These parameters were chosen to increase sensitivity to anthropogenic noises (e.g., engine sounds, gunshots, machinery). The software identified 78 clusters, which we then reviewed manually to verify the accuracy of automated grouping. Among them, 17 clusters contained samples representing the same type of sound, with a match level of $\geq 80\%$. Animal calls (e.g., owls, woodpeckers) and anthropogenic noise such as gunshots clustered best.

Statistical analysis

To assess the effect of distance from linear infrastructure edge on the values of individual indices, we fitted generalized linear mixed-effects models (GLMMs, Gamma family, log link, “lme4” package (Bates et al. 2015) with an interaction between distance from the edge and type of edge (border, road), both as categorical variables, and location ID as a random factor. For NDSI we ran two models; one with the full range of index values, and other with only values below 0, i.e. those indicating higher anthropogenic sound disturbances. To test the difference in the frequency of anthropogenic sounds (gunshots) at different distances from the border edge, we used a chi-square test.

Results

A total of 187,726 recordings were obtained from the six border sites (combined) and 32,356 from the single forest road site.

Acoustic Indices (ADI, AEI, and NDSI)

- **ADI and AEI**

Analyses of ADI and AEI showed no significant variation among the different distances (15m, 100m, 250m, 500m), neither at the border sites nor along the road. Neither index discriminated effectively between sites closer to or farther from anthropogenic sound sources.

- **NDSI**

- At the border sites, the lowest NDSI values were generally observed at 100 m ($p < 0.001$, Fig. 27). However, no significant difference in NDSI was found between the border transects as a whole and the forest road transect.
- At the road site, the lowest NDSI value occurred at 500m, but this trend did not differ significantly from the border sites; however, due to too small sample size (just one transect/one road site), we regard this as illustrative data.
- When focusing on values of NDSI below 0 (indicative of strong anthropogenic influence), the lowest readings at the border were observed at 250m ($p < 0.001$, Fig. 28).

Gunshot Detection

- Across all border transects, a total of 104 gunshots were recorded, whereas only 20 gunshots were detected at the road site.
- When analyzing the distribution of gunshot detections by distance from the border (excluding the road site), significantly more shots were recorded at 100m compared to the other distances ($p < 0.05$, Fig. 29). This pattern aligns with the NDSI results, indicating anthropogenic disturbances permeate the forest at least up to 250m from the edge of the border zone.

Interpretation and Discussion

Our findings suggest that anthropogenic noise from the border area—particularly gunshots and vehicle sounds—penetrates at least 250 m into the forest. The relatively low NDSI values at 100 m and 250 m point to a clear influence of border-related activities on the local soundscape. Interestingly, NDSI did not drop to its lowest values at “0” m (i.e., adjacent to the border), possibly due to the orientation and placement of the ARUs. Microphones positioned close to the source might have had directional biases or obstructions affecting recordings.

Furthermore, the lack of a clear difference at 500m does not necessarily confirm that the sound impact ends by that distance; rather, we lack a completely undisturbed “deep forest” reference site for comparison; or, this may be the distance at which noise from the border balances out with noise generated by roads or other anthropogenic features within the forest. Additional reference points further inside the forest would be beneficial to confirm the acoustic threshold of anthropogenic disturbance.

Although both ADI and AEI can be useful for assessing overall acoustic diversity and evenness, they did not discriminate changes in the soundscape across these sites. By contrast, NDSI—designed to highlight anthropophony versus biophony—proved more sensitive in revealing variations in anthropogenic disturbance.

Conclusions and Recommendations

1. **Dominance of NDSI:** NDSI emerged as the most informative index for detecting and quantifying anthropogenic noise in this winter survey.
2. **Extent of Anthropogenic Influence:** Gunshot and vehicle sounds were detectable up to at least 250 m from the border, suggesting that border activities alter the soundscape well into the forest interior.
3. **Future Placement of ARUs:** To improve detection consistency, it is advisable not to position recording units too close to major noise sources. Instead, placing microphones at various offsets and orientations may offer a more accurate reflection of sound propagation. This is a refinement of a recommendation from the pilot survey.
4. **Necessity of Reference Sites:** Including reference points deeper within the forest (beyond 500m and/or sufficiently away from additional anthropogenic sound sources) would help distinguish natural baseline conditions from anthropogenic disturbances more conclusively.

Overall, our winter recordings indicate that the border infrastructure exerts a measurable acoustic footprint within the forest, with NDSI serving as the most reliable metric for capturing these effects. Future work may explore additional acoustic or statistical methods, as well as year-round datasets, to better understand how seasonal changes in biophony and weather conditions might interact with and modulate anthropogenic noise.

Fig. 27 Effect of distance from linear infrastructure on Normalized Difference Soundscape Index (NDSI) values (full range of index values, i.e. -1 to 1).

Fig. 28 Effect of distance from linear infrastructure on Normalized Difference Soundscape Index (NDSI) values. Analysis was conducted on a range of NDSI values below 0 (i.e. values range -1 to 0).

Fig. 29 Histogram of number of gunshots recorded in relation to distance to border edge.

Long-term forest soundscape monitoring

The goal of this portion of the sound study was to conduct longer-term (eight months) acoustic measurement and assess the variability of the soundscape at different distances from the border throughout the entire vegetation season in a natural forest environment, starting before the season's onset. We carried out acoustic monitoring throughout the entire vegetation season

in the most natural part of the forest, within the strict reserve of Białowieża National Park—an area least impacted by human activity.

Here, we present preliminary results based on data collected during spring and summer (March to July), while recordings from the later period (August to October) are still undergoing acoustic analysis.

Field setup

Between March and October, three Song Meter Mini recorders (Wildlife Acoustics) were deployed in the strict reserve of Białowieża National Park. The recorders were installed on the same trees as the camera traps (Fig. 30) some 3m above ground with microphones directed towards the border. The recorders operated continuously, capturing 5-minute samples every hour at a sampling rate of 32 kHz with a gain setting of 12. They were positioned at different distances from the state border: 15m, 250m, and 500m.

Acoustic analyses

Analyses were conducted in Wildlife Acoustics Kaleidoscope Pro software (version 5.6.8).

Acoustic indices: The recorded sounds were analyzed from spring to summer using the same acoustic indices and parameters as in the above described portion of the study with Audio Moths.

Fig. 30 Song meter installation in same tree as camera trap.

The Normalized Difference Soundscape Index (NDSI) was calculated for the 1,000–8,000 Hz frequency range (anthrophony: 1,000–2,000 Hz, biophony: 2,000–8,000 Hz). Additionally, to explore potential correlations between anthropogenic sounds—such as gunshots, traffic noise, and human voices—and specific acoustic index values, both Anthropophony Index (ADI) and Acoustic Evenness Index (AEI) were calculated within the 250–1,500 Hz frequency range.

Cluster Classification: To further investigate patterns in soundscape composition, a cluster analysis was performed to group recordings based on frequency and amplitude characteristics.

The primary focus was on identifying anthropogenic sounds within the 0–2,000 Hz range, including vehicle noise, gunshots, and human voices. The clustering parameters were set as follows: minimum frequency 100 Hz, maximum frequency 1,500 Hz, minimum duration 1 s, maximum duration 10 s, and maximum gap 0 s.

This analysis identified 6,120 sound events categorized into 77 clusters. A subset of at least 20 recordings per cluster was manually reviewed, totaling over 1,500 recordings. Each identified sound was manually assigned to a category to determine the proportion of recognizable sound types within each cluster. The method effectively grouped distinct biological sounds such as owl calls and woodpecker drumming demonstrating its potential for automated identification of species territories. Anthropogenic sounds such as gunshots were also effectively grouped. However, anthropogenic noises from vehicles and human activity were distributed across multiple clusters, likely due to their strong dependence on distance from the source. This effect was clearly visible in woodpecker drumming, where loud drumming clustered well, but faint drumming was more dispersed.

Results

The total number of identified anthropogenic sound events was twice as high near the border compared to deeper forest locations, with 427, 210, and 213 events recorded at 0m, 250m, and 500m, respectively (Fig. 31). However, the values of NDSI, ADI, and AEI did not correlate with the number of anthropogenic disturbances. This suggests that in a biologically rich soundscape during the vegetation season (e.g., high bird vocal activity), these indices may become less sensitive to anthropogenic noise.

Interpretation and conclusions

Summer data align with winter findings, confirming that the 250 m buffer zone near the border is significantly louder than the forest interior; the impact of intensive bird vocal activity on acoustic indices highlights the need for further refinement. Additional analyses and measurements are planned to address these challenges in future research.

Fig. 31 Histogram of number of total human-related sounds recorded in relation to distance to border edge.

A recent sample of the level of anthrophony at the border can be listened to here and represents a period during which additional fortification was being added to the existing border barrier (in October 2024):

https://soundcloud.com/katarzyna-nowak-14/20241025_110000_sounds-from-the-border-strict-reserve_bpn_2024?utm_source=clipboard&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=social_sharing

Analysis of the autumn to winter data is pending.

Bird community

The bird community was also preliminarily analyzed. Recordings were analyzed using the birdNet classifier from Cornell lab (Kahl et al., 2021), with a minimal confidence of 0.70. While classifications were not verified due to our analytical limitations, errors of the classifier will be consistent across the 3 distances. Observations were grouped into one observation per species per day, and analysed using a PERMANOVA (999 permutations, vegan-package (Oksanen et al., 2022)). This results in a problem, as normally, grouping would be into one observation per species per site, but since this is just one site, date was used for grouping. This likely enlarges the difference observed between the sites, because if a bird has a territory near one site, it will be recorded most of the days and therefore increase the difference with the other sites. It was not yet checked which bird taxa are driving this difference.

The three sites were significantly different from each other ($p < 0.01$), with 250m and 500m less different from each other ($p = 0.005$, $F = 2.98$), and 0 meter being the most different from both 250m and 500m ($p = 0.001$, $F = 11.7$ and $p = 0.001$, $F = 14.7$) with a higher F-value indicating higher dissimilarity. In other words, even though all 3 points are different from each other (possibly due to bird territories), at the edge ("0"m) the bird community is substantially more different compared to the forest interior. This may be the effect of the border. Figure 32 of NMDS illustrates this difference but should be interpreted with caution for now as these results are a very preliminary indication that the border may affect the bird community composition. This could be the result of the 'edge effect' of the open space created by the border road and the barrier, as well as the effect of increased human activity (e.g., vehicle traffic, talking, gunshots). However, to find appropriate evidence for this effect, recordings should be collected at multiple sites in the forest along the border during spring and early summer (i.e. during the time of the peak of the vocal activity of birds). In addition, the amount of anthropogenic noise should be quantified in more detail (e.g., to assess direct effects of anthropogenic sounds on bird vocalisations).

Fig. 32 NMDS output of the bird community at 0, 250 and 500 m from the border based on data from 13 March 11 June 2024, song meter at one location in the strict reserve. Stress = 0.24 and no best solution was obtained. Hence, the figure should be treated as merely an illustration. Please refer to the PERMANOVA output for statistical evidence (vegan-package (Oksanen et al., 2022)).

Noise generated by barrier infrastructure

We did not find evidence that the barrier is generating its own sound although during plant transects in August/September 2024, we could hear the fence expanding/contracting on hot days so it is possible that the infrastructure is and will generate sound (as described by our U.S. colleague about the US-MX border wall on windy days). According to our international partner Myles Traphagen, many parts of the US-Mexico borderlands in North America are prone to high winds. As such, the 9.5m high steel border wall effectively acts as a sail because at the top of the wall is a flat steel plate called an anti-climb plate or wedge. Wind velocities are higher with increasing elevation and the steel fence experiences high shaking during high wind events. This results in the structure shaking and producing what could be described as an industrial sound. Metal is uncommon in nature, and the presence of this sound casts a long sound shadow across the mostly open landscape where sparse vegetation exists to break up the sound. Many observers have reported low frequency sounds during windy conditions using adjective words like “eery,” “odd,” and “out of place.” Even on calm days the steel structure can suddenly buckle and make a loud steel crashing sound that startles birds and humans alike. The mechanics of this are not well understood and should be the subject of further investigation.

As the barrier in BF is largely in a forested ecosystem, the wind velocity is dampened by trees on either side of the border strip; therefore, the barrier is unlikely to generate as much sound as the barrier on the much more exposed US-MX border.

Temperature—4 sites, 2 at border, 2 at road

Temperature and light measurements were made in two places along the border and two places along a control road (Zwierzyniecka Road). We had 18 thermologgers and they were initially placed in the strict reserve at heights of 2m in 3 rows spaced 100 meters apart at the following distances from the border: at the border (first tree from the secondary barrier/edge tree; Fig. 33), and then 5m, 10m, 25m, 50m, 100m from the edge tree. Devices were installed on the eastern side of tree trunks.

After a ~2-week sampling period, 10 of these thermologgers were left in place (the center row of 6 and then 2 in the adjacent rows at the edge and 25m) and 8 of these were moved to Zwierzyniecka Road where they were aligned in a T configuration (6 in a center row and 1 each in adjacent row at the edge) in two locations for 2-3 weeks each. After this, the T was moved to our plot in the northern part of BNP where it was also left for a period of approximately 2 weeks (Table 2). During this sampling along the road and BNP, the T of 10 loggers remained in place in the strict reserve until December.

Canopy density measurements were taken at each tree congruent with the temperature sampling period (Fig. 33). Five measurements were taken under the tree: one in each of the four cardinal directions and one directly under the thermologger. The mean of these five measurements was calculated and regarded as representing the canopy density / light available at that location.

Fig. 33 Example of border-adjacent thermologger (in upper right of photo) and canopy density measurement being taken under the tree with a light meter.

Table 2. Temperature sampling phases.

Location	Phase 1: 3 rows	No loggers	Phase 2: T configurations	No loggers	Setting
Strict Reserve	16/5/2024 00:00 to 30/5/2024 23:55	18	30/5/2024 23:55 to 02/12/2024 09:00	10	5MIN (Phase 1) SMART (Phase 2)
Zwierzyniecka-location 1	/	/	05/06/2024 16:00 to 26/06/2024 10:00	8	5MIN
Zwierzyniecka-location 2	/	/	26/6/2024 16:00 to 22/7/2024 9:00	8	5MIN
BPN	/	/	22/7/2024 16:00 to 12/8/2024 12:00	8	5MIN

For the analysis, only data from May to August 2024 were compared for the four sites. The goal was to compare the edge effect within site, or the difference in temperature between the edge and forest interior (Fig. 34) rather than between site comparisons given differences in sampling dates and site characteristics. Indeed, all edge thermologgers registered higher maximum (Fig. 34) and mean (Fig. 35) temperatures than forest interior loggers.

Fig. 34 Maximum temperature at 0 and 100 by location for the dates 15-05 to 12-08.

Fig. 35 At all four sites sampled, mean temperature was hotter at the edge than at 100m into the forest.

The largest difference between the edge and 100m temperature was in the strict reserve where the difference was 1 degree C; then BPN at 0.6 degrees C, Zwierzyniecka 2 with a difference of 0.4 degrees C and lastly Zwierzyniecka 1 with 0.2 degrees C difference; this lattermost site was deemed an outlier because of wet habitat/a patch of alder bog that is found just near the road and which evidently lowers temperature (Figs. 35-36).

The data from May 15 to August 12, 2024 yielded 445,970 records from the four locations. We used the lme4 and lmerTest packages in R to fit a linear mixed-effects model via restricted maximum likelihood (REML) to investigate the effects of distance from the edge (0 to 100m), edge type (border, road), and mean canopy cover on temperature.

The distance from edge coefficient was -0.00424, suggesting a decrease in temperature as distance from the edge increased. Factors also contributing to temperature included canopy density and edge type, with edge type showing no significant effect (no difference between the road and the border). Increasing distance from the edge was associated with a slight decrease in temperature. Increasing mean canopy cover was associated with a larger decrease in temperature. Edge type (border vs road) did not significantly differ. There is some variability in baseline temperatures among the 4 locations (as shown by the random intercept for LOC; Table 3B). In sum, during the summer period, both distance from the edge and the extent of canopy cover are important in predicting temperature, whereas the specific type of edge does not seem to have a significant impact (Table 3A).

Fig. 36 Differences in temperature registered between thermologgers at consecutive distances from the edge: 0m and 5m, 5m and 10m, 10m and 25m, 25m and 50m, 50m and 100m, across the four sampling locations: BNP, Strict Reserve in BNP, northern and southern Zwierzyniecka Road.

We expanded the model to also include time of day (Table 3A). Night-time temperatures were about 6 units lower than daytime. Additional models were run, to check for an interaction between distance from the edge and time of day; it was found that during the day, the effect of distance from edge is much bigger than at night (daytime effect is -0.008 whereas during the night it is only -0.0004). A separate model was then run just on the day data. While the full model demonstrates how nighttime temperatures significantly drop, the day-only model highlights the significant negative impact on temperature of distance from edge and negligible effects of edge type.

In the full model incorporating both day and night observations, time of day was a dominant predictor, with nighttime temperatures averaging about 6.3 units lower than daytime temperatures. Notably, the interaction between distance from the edge and time of day revealed that distance significantly affected temperature only during the day (with a daytime slope of approximately -0.008 per unit distance), while its effect at night was essentially negligible. In contrast, the day-only model confirmed a robust negative relationship between distance from the edge and temperature (estimate ≈ -0.0066), along with a significant cooling effect of increasing canopy cover. In both models, the effect of edge type remained non-significant, and the between-location variability was moderate. Overall, these comparisons suggest that the

impact of distance from the edge on temperature is largely a daytime phenomenon, with diurnal differences driving much of the variance observed in the full model (Fig. 37).

Table 3A Fixed effects included distance from edge (m), edge type (border, road), mean canopy cover and time of day (day, night).

Predictor	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	p value
(Intercept)	25.26	1.119	22.576	0.0021 **
Distance_from_edge	-0.00424	0.0001841	-23.017	p < 0.001 ***
Edge_typeroad	-0.3755	1.576	-0.238	0.8341
Mean_canopy	-0.05636	0.001483	-38.017	p < 0.001 ***
Time_of_daynight	-6.277	0.01011	-621.018	p < 0.001 ***

Table 3B Random LOC was the four sites in which temperature and light were measured.

Grouping Factor	Effect	Variance	Std. Dev.
LOC	(Intercept)	2.482	1.576
Residual		11.388	3.375

Fig. 37 Mean temperature at the edge and 100 meters into the forest for day (left) and night (right) across the four sampling locations.

When it comes to temperature at the edge, the state border appears to be behaving like a road. There was no straightforward way to evaluate whether the steel barrier contributes in some way to this edge effect. However, it is likely that the hotter edge, in some combination with the barriers on the border, together contribute to the success of thermophilic, alien, non-forest, plant species described in the next section.

Plant Transects—along the state border

While the focus of “barrier ecology” is typically on large mammals, border barriers also affect plant communities (Su et al. 2003). At the US-Mexico border, saguaro cacti (*Carnegiea gigantea*), a cultural keystone plant species of Native Nations in particular the Tohono O'odham, and a symbol of the southwestern United States, were among the most adversely affected plants and attempts at transplanting them were unsuccessful (Fig. 38, photos shared by our international partner Myles Traphagen).

Invasive plants have also taken root on the US-MX border (US GAO report: <https://www.gao.gov/products/gao-23-105443>). Some of these include the same “weedy” genera as we recorded along the PL-BY border during this study including *Agrostis*, *Echinochloa*, *Polygonum*, *Rumex*, and *Sonchus* (Traphagen, unpublished data), which may be native in our part of the world but still typify non-forest, open habitats.

Fig. 38 Saguaro cacti, a native species, underwent damages due to the US-Mexico border wall (left). Attempts to transplant them (right), were unsuccessful. *Photo Credit: Myles Traphagen*

In August 2024, we carried out plant transects in 6 locations along the border recording non-forest, thermophilic, pioneer, alien and invasive species. Plant transects were carried out

directly along the border and also 50m away from the border. On transects directly along the border, we recorded if plants occur in the forest, within the secondary barriers (forest net and concertina) along the border road—forest side or along the border road—main barrier side. In addition to these four location categories (Fig. 39), we recorded abundance scale 1-8 which represented 1, up to 10, 10, more than 10, up to 100, more than 100, up to 1000, and more than 1000 individuals.

We sampled in dry, mesic and wet habitats in two locations each along the border for a total of 6 sample sites. Transects were 800-m long / plot lengths were 100m long (we used the poles making up the electronic barrier to demarcate plot lengths). We sampled mainly in State Forest with a small segment through a nature reserve (Starzyna) because BPN has carried out mitigation along the border road in the form of invasive species monitoring and removal since the barrier construction year (2022).

We recorded 136 plant species meeting our criteria (i.e. non-forest, thermophilic, pioneer, alien and/or invasive species) both along the border and in the forest. Of these, 130 species were detected on the border and 6 only in the forest. Thirty species or 23.1% of those that were found on the border were also found 50 meters into the forest. While our species accumulation curves began to asymptote (Fig. 40), more sampling would have very likely resulted in the addition of further species, also given the differences between sample areas especially mesic 1 and mesic 2 (Fig. 41 of jaccard distances).

Fig. 39 Species richness by forest type (dry, mesic, wet) and location along the border (forest, secondary barriers, road (forest side), road (main barrier side). Secondary barriers appeared to support high species richness across the three forest types (dry, mesic, wet).

Fig. 40 Species accumulation curves in the 6 locations sampled. Dry2 was least close to asymptote, while wet2 was closest to asymptote.

Fig. 41 Jaccard Distance Matrix showing that sample areas “wet 1” and “wet 2” were most similar to each other while “mesic 2” and “wet 1” were least similar to each other.

Of species on the border, 13 were evaluated as having invasion potential (Tables 4-5; Fig. 42). Alien plants (with invasion potential) included *Conyza canadensis*, *Solidago canadensis* and *Bidens frondosa*. Three of the species with invasion potential found on the border were also detected inside the forest: *Solidago canadensis*, *Bidens frondosa* and *Acer pseudoplatanus* (Fig. 43). For the lattermost of these, northeastern Poland is out of its range.

Table 4. Plant species with invasion or expansion potential inventoried on 48 100-meter transects along the state border between Poland and Belarus. Abundance categories refer to 100-m transects.

Taxon	Type	Abundance (individuals)					Total
		1	<10	<100	<1000	>1000	
<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	local kenophyte	2	4	3	-	-	9
<i>Bidens frondosa</i>	kenophyte	4	9	-	7	2	22
<i>Coryza canadensis</i>	kenophyte	2	7	16	16	2	43
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	archaeophyte	2	2	-	-	-	4
<i>Erigeron sp.</i>	kenophyte	9	8	1	-	-	18
<i>Galinsoga ciliata</i>	kenophyte	-	1	1	-	-	2
<i>Lupinus polyphyllus</i>	kenophyte	-	1	-	-	-	1
<i>Malus domestica</i>	kenophyte	1	-	-	-	-	1
<i>Oxalis sp.</i>	kenophyte	-	1	-	-	-	1
<i>Sambucus racemosa</i>	local kenophyte	1	-	-	-	-	1
<i>Sarothamnus scoparius</i>	local kenophyte	2	2	1	-	-	5
<i>Setaria pumila</i>	archaeophyte	4	13	4	-	-	21
<i>Solidago canadensis</i>	kenophyte	14	16	7	-	-	37
Total		41	64	33	23	4	165
%		24.9	38.8	20.0	13.9	2.4	100

Table 5. Frequency of detecting plant species with invasion or expansion potential across four zones of the state border strip between Poland and Belarus.

Taxon	Forest edge	Secondary barriers	Road, forest side	Road, main barrier side	Total
<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	8	5	1	-	14
<i>Bidens frondosa</i>	16	17	9	-	42
<i>Coryza canadensis</i>	26	30	30	9	95
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	-	2	2	-	4
<i>Erigeron sp.</i>	6	10	3	4	23
<i>Galinsoga ciliata</i>	-	-	2	-	2
<i>Lupinus polyphyllus</i>	1	-	-	-	1
<i>Malus domestica</i>	-	1	-	-	1
<i>Oxalis sp.</i>	-	1	-	-	1
<i>Sambucus racemosa</i>	-	1	1	-	2
<i>Sarothamnus scoparius</i>	5	2	-	-	7
<i>Setaria pumila</i>	8	13	11	3	35
<i>Solidago canadensis</i>	18	21	16	5	60
Total	88	103	75	21	287
%	30.7	35.9	26.1	7.3	100

Fig. 42 Maximum abundance (interval scale of 1-8) of invasive plants by survey area (two dry, two mesic, two wet) also by location on the border.

Fig. 43 Three invasive plants found both along the border and the forest transect 50m into the forest.

Presence of plants such as *Acer pseudoplatanus* are associated with their decorative character, owing to which they were planted in the parks of Białowieża and escaped to the

forest but their current presence along the border could be exacerbated by the fortification/militarization activities. Archeofits included *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Lactuca serriola*, *Setaria pumila*, *Silene latifolia* and *Solanum nigrum*.

The majority of plants recorded are benefiting from the “secondary barriers” specifically the space in between the forest net and concertina because it excludes ungulate browsing (Fig. 44). In addition, climbing taxa (such as *Fallopia*, *Solanum*, *Convolvulus*) are using the forest net and even concertina (Fig. 45).

Fig. 44 Three invasive species *Solidago canadensis* (left), *Conyza canadensis* (middle), and *Bidens frondosa* (right) benefiting from the secondary barriers on the border.

Fig. 45 Climbing plants using the secondary barriers: *Fallopia* (top left), *Solanum* (bottom left) and *Convolvulus* (right)

While we recorded *Impatiens parviflora* along the border during dung/sign transects in 2023 in one of the above transect locations, we did not detect it in any of our sample areas in 2024 (which could be the result of BNP interventions in the form of invasive plant removal); another species we recorded at the end of Browska Road during other monitoring, *Corispermum leptopterum* (<https://www.iop.krakow.pl/ias/gatunki/73>), we also did not detect during the above transect work. Again, it is unlikely that we captured all invasive and alien species in the less than 5 km sampled.

In 2023, we observed tomato fruits in one place along the border while in 2024, we observed tomatoes in several locations, largely in association with outposts (Fig. 46).

Fig. 46 Tomato plants first observed in 2023 (left) and thought to possibly be a one-off were later observed in late 2024 (right) during plant transects in several locations next to outposts; their presence further attests to the effects of anthropogenic activities on the assemblage of plants growing along the border.

In addition, mosses that typify sidewalks and weedy species that colonize bare, disturbed, nutrient-rich soils including old bonfire sites such as *Funaria hygrometrica* were observed (Fig. 47). These “border mosses” were also inventoried, as part of a PhD thesis being carried out at BSG.

Fig. 47 *Funaria hygrometrica* growing on concrete left over from the construction period.

While further analysis is pending, the plant survey data have been made openly available on Zenodo and shared with relevant persons including staff from Białowieża National Park to facilitate a quicker potential response or intervention: <https://zenodo.org/records/14472017> (other NAWA data will also be made available on Zenodo).

Important Resources Near the Border

There may be important resources in the vicinity of the border such as wallows, mineral sites, and waterholes (such as the one pictured in Fig. 48 discovered 50m from the border during plant surveys).

Fig. 48 Extensive waterhole 50m from the state border below Browska Road. Note that at this waterhole, we recorded *Bidens frondosa* possibly carried on animal fur to or from the nearby border area.

We do not for instance know what important resources might be found in the habitat pockets between our border and the Belarusian sistema which is an area of 37 sq km (larger than the area occupied by the city of Siedlce, which supports >77,000 human inhabitants). We know energy expenditure of jaguars at the US-MX border was high as they searched for gaps to

access water springs (Chambers et al. 2022); we also know of a Mexican wolf which spent 5 days walking along the US-MX border wall possibly in search of a mate (Main 2022).

Summary of Results

Combinations of methods under challenging conditions can yield unique insights at different scales. Indeed this was our experience during this study. Our findings are summarized as follows:

- Less animal sign was detected at border and road edges (transect data) with deer dung being the main animal sign detected at intermediate 100-250 m distances
- Trash (plastics, cans) was the dominant human sign (with five times as much trash at border than road areas), followed by cut trees and building materials (the latter two only detected at border sites)
- Human presence exceeded animal presence at the border sites (camera trap data)
- Some wild animal taxa are more night active near the border than they are near roads (camera trap data)
- Mesocarnivores (up to red fox size) are passing through the secondary barriers and likely the main barrier (snow-tracking, ad hoc discussions with soldiers)
- Anthropogenic sound penetrates 100-250 m into the forest (sound sampling with audio moths)
- Bird community at the border edge may be distinct from the bird community 250-500m into the forest (sound sampling with song meters)
- Border and road edges are hotter than the forest interior with temperature dropping with increasing distance from edge and increasing canopy cover (temperature and light measurements) but BF shows some resilience to this edge effect at night
- The border has become colonized by thermophilic, non-forest, pioneer and alien plant species and 20% of these are also found 50 m into the forest interior including three of the 13 invasive species detected on the border (plant surveys)
- There are important resources near the border including waterholes, access to which may be affected by ongoing human activities (militarization, further fortification, construction, noise, vehicle traffic, etc.)
- Potential for future restoration of connectivity must be considered in decision-making going forward; one criterion might be to direct efforts where a rare or umbrella species is concentrating. Bison were recorded both at the border and observed (by uniformed services) to approach the barrier from the BY side at our northernmost site

In summary, we found that there is a suite of ecological effects associated with the militarization and fortification of the border. Likely a cumulative effects framework will need to be adopted to understand for example animal avoidance behavior and loss of habitat functionality (Eftestøl et al. 2021). Some of these effects may be long-lasting.

Threat Overview

Several distinct but interconnected and cumulative threats are associated with the border fortification and militarization:

- 1) road risks
- 2) barrier effects
- 3) militarization

1) The border is both a road and a hard barrier. When we began our research, the border road was not yet fenced and there was a possibility of wildlife-barrier and wildlife-road interactions (including wildlife-vehicle collisions, not just on the myriad of forest roads that lead to the border but also on the border road itself), something we did not assess directly in this study. Once the additional barriers were erected, this cut off access of large mammals to the border road, as well as restricted access of uniformed services to the forest. This may have had some benefits for the wildlife and environment. Still, however, there is human-wildlife interaction (at outposts), vehicle noise, pollution with emissions and vehicle fluids, deposition of road maintenance materials (possibly especially in alder bog areas) bringing with it potential invasive and alien plant species, changes in animal movement behavior and predator-prey interactions, and edge effects.

2) Barrier effects: large mammals are unable to cross the barriers. Evidence from the PL-BY border (e.g., <https://niechzyja.pl/concertina-zabija-raport/>), also Slovenia-Croatia border (Pokorny et al. 2017, Safner et al. 2021) shows that wildlife may injure themselves or die in barriers and specifically on razor wire, being used in BF for added fortification including running it along the ground and along the center of the barrier. We recall one early account from Border Guard about a roe deer ramming itself against the main barrier (prior to installation of the secondary barriers) and getting his antlers stuck; soldiers apparently dislodged it successfully. It is not currently known if smaller mammals such as foxes and badgers, which are managing to cross barriers, are doing so without injury. The barrier effects are also contributing to edge effects at least indirectly for example given the tree cutting associated with further fortification.

3) Human activities are resulting in changes in human-wildlife interactions. Activities include burning of fires, tree cutting, discarding of food (slices of bread, fruits (citrus, banana peels), fish cans/tins, candy bar wrappers, etc.) and garbage disposal in areas of patrols. The garbage attracts animals like foxes, marten and raccoon dogs. Plastic pollution (in some areas 1 piece of garbage every 10m) likely means microplastics have entered the environment on a bigger scale than previous to the situation on the border. Perhaps animals are helping to spread garbage which may have been bagged but the bag was then not removed promptly enough. Prior to portable toilets being brought to the border, there were human latrines up to 100m from the border road which posed a disease risk (reverse zoonoses) however this is mostly rectified since winter 2023/2024. The building of temporary or semi-permanent structures out of wood and even concrete and other materials (shelters, outposts) is a further activity, also partly rectified with current use of pre-fabricated outposts. Noise is a factor and on a number of

occasions, we heard loud music blasting from outposts. While the discarded food may act to habituate some species, others are displaced from the border area even up to 250m (on one camera trap at 250m from the border, we had a photo of 3 bison running followed by uniformed service personnel). Military dogs off-leash and (possibly feral) dogs are drawn to outposts in protected areas of BF (photos from camera traps and encounters). Attraction of domestic cats into the border zone is also occurring and soldiers report cats visiting them even from the BY side; in addition to pathogen transmission risk, cats may increase bird and bird nest predation along the border edge.

Other considerations:

- Concertina fence is protected on only one side by forest netting and the accidental entry of an animal and its flushing between the barriers could cause injury or fatality if animal tries to escape back to the forest through the concertina
- Constant human presence in this environment is already a violation of the basic objectives of creating such a sanctuary
- Multiple commutes, successive shifts during the day to outposts and back to the base means constant vehicle traffic
- Deliberate feeding of animals at military posts with food products, building feeders for this purpose must cease
- Numerous traces of wild and domestic animals near the outposts are evidence of the creation of concentrations of animals that should not be there
- Littering and disposal of leftover packaging and food also outside the places of posts. Waste should be taken out of the forest in timely way
- Deep holes in the ground from use of soil from the forest for the construction/maintenance of infrastructure (Fig. 49) (e.g., border road maintenance)
- Storage or abandonment of construction materials in BF, including, which is very dangerous for animals and people moving through the forest, coils of razor wire, especially dangerous after snowfall when they get covered and are not easily visible
- Purposeful interaction or habituation of wildlife; recently (2025), a hole in the concertina fence around an outpost was observed and from communication with uniformed service personnel, we understood it had been cut to allow direct passage to the outpost for a fox.

Fig. 49 Hole near the border likely made for excavation of material for road maintenance. Jan. 2025 on transect with Nuria Selva in an area south of Browska Road.

Recommendations

- Carry out land cover change analysis associated with the border infrastructure
- Allow camera traps to face barrier so that a barrier analysis / wildlife interactions with barriers can be better understood (for example Xu et al. 2021 classed animal-barrier encounters into six behaviour categories: *quick cross*, *average movement*, *bounce*, *back-and-forth*, *trace* and *trapped*)

- Consider allowing researchers access to video data of wildlife from the electronic barrier; the data could be provided for scientific analysis with a time lag and excluding human data
- Integrate NAWA with other available data (including camera-trap based) from other field studies to better understand impacts on wildlife of the border fortification/militarization
- Further investigate how BF-typical soundscape may be altered by changes in intensity in human activities and in turn how this may affect animal behavior and risk response distances, and functional habitat
- Consider removing secondary barriers (forest net and concertina) to allow for browsing by deer and other taxa on potentially invasive plants
- Coordinate with Białowieża National Park which was/is removing or controlling alien and invasive plant species on the border road along the park (ideally this activity would be carried out along and if possible beyond the 53.4 km where BF runs along the border)
- Conduct plant surveys several times per year along the border road and into the forest interior (to at least 50m) to enable early detection of possible invasive species before they spread and to monitor efficacy of mitigation methods
- Reduce to extent possible vehicle traffic along border road and all forest roads at night (presume that no diel activity shifts are currently possible by wildlife near to border because military activities extend into night time hours so animals have little to no relief). Keeping the night quiet and dark is one suggested way of minimizing effects on wildlife
- Cease high risk contact between people and wildlife: human interaction with mesocarnivores; discourage domestic animals from visiting outposts (don't feed any animals in the forest, wild or domestic); understand pathogen transmission risk
- Understand role of animals that interact with the border such as red foxes in spreading invasive species such as *B. frondosa*
- Plan future wildlife crossings (including by opening gates in the barrier intended for this purpose, Fig. 50) which might be sighted in the vicinity of where animals may tend to aggregate for example at waterholes or where, for instance, the sistema is close to the Polish barrier or where ungulates were seen approaching the barriers from both sides. PL-BY might cooperate on opening sections of both fences in the spirit of an "Ecological Peace Corridor" (Cazzolla-Gatti 2025)
- Conduct survey with soldiers stationed at the border to learn about their wildlife sightings, wildlife barrier crossing behaviors, human-wildlife interactions, other observations that can inform mitigation
- Consider other values in addition to national security as part of the "Eastern Shield" for example nature conservation and human-nature connection
- In planning additional fortification, take environmental costs into account and mitigation potential (which remains unassessed) and follow mitigation hierarchy (avoid, minimize, offset):
 1. avoidance of a harmful activity (e.g., the activity does not take place in the protected area);
 2. minimize the impact of the activity (e.g., conditions included on any permit);
 3. habitat compensation, where avoidance and minimization are not possible

- Heed findings from other borders e.g. US-Mexico (US GAO report: <https://www.gao.gov/products/gao-23-105443> because we already know much about harm caused by border barriers around the world but are not mobilizing this existing knowledge as precaution
- Develop holistic approaches for example a One Health approach given the complexity of the situation (see Fig. 51 in additional outputs) and evidence that anthropogenic disturbances (such as linear infrastructure) that result in degraded habitats / fragmentation of forest together with a warming climate elevate zoonotic disease risk e.g., tick-borne diseases (Iijima et al. 2025)
- Include ecologists in current and future discussions and prepare together a SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound) management approach on the border

Fig. 50 A closed gate seen during snow-track surveys (winter 2024). According to the UNESCO (2024) mission report, there are three such gates in Białowieża Forest.

Fig. 51 Problem tree attempting a holistic One Health approach to analyzing the border situation; solutions to these problems are needed with increased cooperation across various sectors. Included in a poster shared at the 2024 One Health symposium in Berlin (https://www.researchgate.net/publication/385072348_One_Health_Threats_on_Poland's_Militarized_Border_in_Bialowieza_Forest).

Changes to initial plans including from unanticipated challenges

Generally, we experienced some similar challenges to those faced by researchers in human conflict-affected areas such as access restrictions, tense interactions with uniformed services, interference with research equipment, tensions between scientific research / conservation priorities and national security (Nowak et al. 2023), limited emergency type funding (other than the NAWA urgency), and a dynamic situation with frequent changes in personnel on the border, road conditions, exclusion zones, etc.

There were a few changes to our original plans reported in change cards to NAWA. Among these were a decision to rent rather than purchase audio equipment and we would recommend this route to other researchers. During our project, we rented both audio (from MRIPAS) and camera trap (OSCF) equipment although we did make some purchases as well of said equipment (3 song meters, 6 camera traps) including to limit our servicing of audio equipment and because of (unanticipated) theft of camera traps. Further, we channeled funds that were going to be unspent (e.g. for open access publication with which we were not going to be ready before the end of the project) for additional GIS work that proved helpful for snow-track data analysis and various cartographic visualizations. We extended the project by 6 months permitting us to inventory plants, repeat most transects, begin more sophisticated data analysis, and accommodate the visit of one of our international colleagues who could not visit until 2025.

While we did not repeat animal dung/sign transects as hoped in autumn 2024, we managed to repeat most of them (6 at border, 3 at roads) in winter 2025. What we did in late summer/autumn 2024 was to inventory plants along the border. Justification for this additional unplanned work is that we decided to channel effort into better understanding potentially invasive plants as the animal data was also being captured with the camera traps.

On account of the length of time it has taken to process existing audio data, a second period of sampling with audio moths was not carried out; however, song meters continued to sample sound in the strict reserve until fall/winter so in essence, we had at least some sampling from throughout 2024. The song meters also allowed for monitoring of sound without too frequent of checks along the border during the exclusion zone period. Still, the spatiotemporal limitations of sound sampling meant that it was not as representative of the situation on the border as we would have liked but this would be challenging to do given how dynamic the situation has been.

Interference and theft of camera traps was one challenge that was eventually officially reported to Hajnówka police; however, we still managed to retain and maintain in the field the majority of camera traps. The six additional acquired cameras replaced those that were stolen or broken. Strong-handedness and inappropriate behavior (photographing personal identification with their cell phone) by the military was reported to Żandarmeria (Białystok); some time delays and stress in the field was associated with such checks and interactions. However, on several other occasions, interactions with uniformed services personnel resulted in useful information and insights gained about wildlife on the border.

We have yet to realize our original plan of preparing a guide for researchers working in other border regions with our international colleagues but still intend to eventually produce this or a related shared output. We did produce other shared outputs in the form of a publication in

an international conservation journal, a book chapter, an article in a local journal, contribution to an expert opinion report, and conference presentations described in the following sections of this report and in several of these, we included such guidelines and recommendations.

Conference presentations

1. European Congress of Conservation Biology in Bologna, Italy—July 2024 (poster)
2. One Health symposium in Berlin, Germany—October 2024 (poster)
3. Badaczki i Badacze na Granicy, Gruski BF region, Poland—January 2025 (talk)

Nowak K, Bubnicki JW, Kuberski Ł, Selva N, Jaroszewicz B, Komar E, Nowak P, Richards SA 2024. Effects of Poland's border militarization on wildlife in Białowieża Primeval Forest—Preliminary findings. Conference: 7th European Congress of Conservation Biology. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/382658378_Effects_of_Poland's_border_militarization_on_wildlife_in_Bialowieza_Primeval_Forest-_Preliminary_findings

Nowak K, Kołodziej-Sobocińska M, Marciniak L, Selva N 2024. One Health Threats on Poland's Militarized Border in Białowieża Forest. One Health Symposium 2024. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/385072348_One_Health_Threats_on_Poland's_Militarized_Border_in_Bialowieza_Forest

Nowak K, Selva N 2025. Understanding the Socio-Ecological Footprint of State Border Militarization. Conference: (23) Seminarium na Granicy: Przyroda w Kryzysie — Badaczki i Badacze na Granicy. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/388185256_Understanding_the_Socio-Ecological_Footprint_of_State_Border_Militarization

Upcoming:

4. Who Needs a Border Wall? Borders, Fences and Walls: Towards a New Research Agenda—2025 Montreal Borders and Borders Walls Conference – 7th Edition—April-May 2025 (hybrid) (online talk)
5. 14th European Vertebrate Management Conference meeting co-organized by our lead Slovenian collaborator Bostjan Pokorny in Slovenia—May 2025 (talk)

Additional outputs

Publications

Nowak K, Bear D, Dutta A, Traphagen M, Zmihorski M, Jaroszewicz B. 2023. Threats to conservation from national security interests. *Conservation Biology* 38: e14193. Available: <https://conbio.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/cobi.14193>

Selva N, Nowak K, Stachowicz I, Kudrenko S. in press. Wildlife research and conservation in conflict-affected areas. Ch. 14 in: *War Impacts on the Environment*. Eds. Paulo Pereira and Damia Barcelo. Springer.

Krenova Z, Nowak K. 2025. Před plotem, za plotem. Jak hraniční bariéry oddělují i spojují. *Šumava Journal* - Volume: spring 2025, pp. 16-17.

Paper topics in preparation:

- Plants on the border—findings from Białowieża Forest on border infrastructure effects on plant community
- Wildlife on the border—combining results from camera-traps, transects, snow-tracking, sound sampling
- Ethnography paper aimed at interpreting convergence of human and animal signs in BF during the border crisis from interdisciplinary perspective

Reports

NAWA data were contributed to an “expert opinion” report prepared by MRIPAS to IOŚ:

Schmidt K, Kowalczyk R, Kołodziej-Sobocińska M, Niedziałkowska M, Tokarska M, Żmihorski M, Nowak K. 2024. Oddziaływanie zapory granicznej na granicy polsko-białoruskiej na Obiekt Światowego Dziedzictwa "Białowieża Forest". Available:

<https://ios.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/ekspertyza-oddziaływanie-zapory-granicznej.pdf>

Media engagements

BBC <https://www.bbc.com/future/article/20241113-how-fences-affect-the-worlds-wildlife>

Oko Press <https://oko.press/zolnierze-na-granicy-niszczaprzyrode-rzad-nie-reaguje>

Wyborcza:

<https://wyborcza.pl/7,75400,31705984,biolozka-media-informuja-tylko-o-potraconych-zubrach-a-w-puszczy.html>

References

- Bates D., Mächler M., Bolker B. M., Walker S. C. 2015. Fitting linear mixed-effects models using lme4. *J. Stat. Softw.* 67. doi:10.18637/jss.v067.i01
- Błaszczyc C., Kempers E.B., Burgers L. 2024. Fenced Europe: A more-than-human perspective to border control. The case of Białowieża. *European Law Open* 3(1): 90-110. doi.org/10.1017/el0.2024.6
- Bradfer-Lawrence T., Gardner N., Bunnefeld L., Bunnefeld N., Willis S.G., Dent D.H. 2019. Guidelines for the use of acoustic indices in environmental research. *Methods Ecol Evol.* 10(10):1796–807.
- Brocada L. & Piana P. 2022. Per Un'ecologia Politica Dei Borderscapes: Il Caso Del Confine Tra Polonia E Bielorussia Nella Foresta Di Białowieża. doi.org/10.19246/DOCUGEO2281-7549/202202_02
- Cazzolla Gatti R. 2025. Ecological Peace Corridors: A new conservation strategy to protect human and biological diversity. *Biological Conservation* 302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2024.110947>
- Chambers S.N., Villarreal M.L., Norman L.M., Bravo J.C., Traphagen M.B. 2022. Spatial models of jaguar energy expenditure in response to border wall construction and remediation. *Frontiers Conserv Sci* 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcosc.2022.1012010>
- Edwards T., Capistrán M.M.E., Traphagen M.B., Sapiens G.-M.M., O'Meara C., Lutz-Ley A., Deloya H.V., Wilder B.T. 2020. Caught in the middle—research in the U.S.-Mexico border region. *SocArXiv t95jm*, Center for Open Science. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/t95jm>
- Eftestøl S., Tsegaye D., Flydal K., Colman J.E. 2021. Cumulative effects of infrastructure and human disturbance: a case study with reindeer. *Landscape Ecology* 36: 2673-2689. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-021-01263-1>
- Harrity E.J., Traphagen M., Bethel M., Facka A.N., Dax M., Burns E. 2024. USA-Mexico border wall impedes wildlife movement. *Frontiers Ecology and Evolution* 12 doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2024.1487911
- Iijima H., Watari Y., Doi K., Yasuo K., Okabe K. 2025. Forest fragmentation and warmer climate increase tick-borne disease infection. *EcoHealth* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10393-025-01702-4>
- Jaroszewicz B., Cholewińska O., Gutowski J.M., Samojlik T., Zimny M., Latałowa M. Białowieża Forest—A Relic of the High Naturalness of European Forests. 2019. *Forests* 10, 849. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f10100849>
- Jaroszewicz B., Nowak K., Żmihorski M. 2021. Poland's Border Wall Threatens Ancient Forest. *Science* 374: 1063. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abn0451>
- Jones I.L., Bull J.W., Milner-Gulland E.J., Esipov A.V., Suttle K.B. 2014. Quantifying habitat impacts of natural gas infrastructure to facilitate biodiversity offsetting. *Ecol Evol* 4: 79-90.
- Kahl S., Wood C.M., Eibl M., Klinck H. 2021. BirdNET: A deep learning solution for avian diversity monitoring. *Ecol. Inform.* 61: 101236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2021.101236>
- Krenova Z., Nowak K. 2025. Před plotem, za plotem. Jak hraniční bariéry oddělují i spojují. *Šumava*. jaro 2025. 16-17.

Large Landscape Conservation (LLC) 2024 Ecological Connectivity in Updated NBSAPs.
<https://largelandscapes.org/wp-content/uploads/Ecological-Connectivity-in-NBSAPs.pdf>

Lawrence M.J., Stemberger H.L.J., Zolderdo A.J., Struthers D.P., Cooke S.J. 2015. The effects of modern war and military activities on biodiversity and the environment. *Environmental Reviews*. 23(4): 443-460. <https://doi.org/10.1139/er-2015-0039>

Lei J. and Wang L. 2025. Border fences threaten movements of large mammals in southwestern China post-COVID-19 pandemic. *Global Ecology and Conservation*, e03410.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2025.e03410>

Liu J., Li Yong D., Choi C.-Y., Gibson L. 2020 Transboundary frontiers: An emerging priority for biodiversity conservation. *TREE* 35: 679-690. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2020.03.004>

Main D. 2022. An endangered wolf went in search of a mate. The border wall blocked him. *National Geographic*, Jan. 21 2022. Available:
<https://www.nationalgeographic.com/animals/article/mexican-gray-wolf-migration-stopped-by-border-wall>

Marneweck C.J., Allen B.L., Butler A.R., Do Linh San E., Harris S.N., Jensen A.J., Saldo E.A., Somers M.J., Titus K., Muthersbaugh M., Vanak A., Jachowski D.S. 2022. Middle-out ecology: small carnivores as sentinels of global change. *Mammal Review* 52: 471-479.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/mam.12300>

McCallum J.W., Rowcliffe J.M., Cuthill I.C. 2014. Conservation on International Boundaries: The Impact of Security Barriers on Selected Terrestrial Mammals in Four Protected Areas in Arizona, USA. *PLoS ONE* 9(4): e93679.

Nowak K., Bear D., Dutta A., Traphagen M., Źmihorski M., Jaroszewicz B. 2023. Threats to conservation from national security interests. *Conserv Biol* 38: e14193.

Nowak K., Olszańska A., Pietrzyk-Kaszyńska A. *et al.* 2025. Border militarization affects people's interactions with nature in Białowieża Forest. *Ambio* 54: 175–183.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-024-02113-5>

Nowak K., Richards S.A., Źmihorski M., Selva N., Wiktoruk A., Gutiérrez-Zapata S., Jaroszewicz B. in review. Footprint of state border infrastructure extends beyond the border: Tree damage and roadkill along a road in Białowieża Forest. Preprint:
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5131748

Oksanen J., Blanchet F.G., Kindt R., Legendre P., Minchin P.R., O'Hara R.B., Solymos P., Stevens M., Szoecs E., Wagner H., Barbour M., Bedward M., Bolker B., Borcard D., Carvalho G., Chirico M., De Caceres M., Durand S., Evangelista H., FitzJohn R., Friendly M., Furneaux B., Hannigan G., Hill M., Lahti L., McGlinn D., Ouellette M., Ribeiro Cunha E., Smith T., Stier A., Ter Braak C., Weedon J., 2022. vegan: Community Ecology Package.

Pijanowski B.C., Villanueva-Rivera L.J., Dumyahn S.L., Farina A., Krause B.L., Napolitano B.M., Gage S.H., Pieretti N. 2011. Soundscape Ecology: The Science of Sound in the Landscape. *BioScience* 61 (3): 203–216. <https://doi.org/10.1525/bio.2011.61.3.6>

Peters R., Ripple W.J., Moskwik M., Wolf C., Carreon-Arroyo G., Ceballos G., Cordova A., Dirzo R., et al. 2018. Nature divided, scientists united: U.S.-Mexico border wall threatens biodiversity and binational conservation. *BioScience* 68 (10): 740–743. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biy063>.

Pokorny B., Flajšman K., Centore L., Krope F.S., Šprem N. 2017. Border fence: a new ecological obstacle for wildlife in Southeast Europe. *European Journal of Wildlife Research* 63: 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10344-016-1074-1>

R Core Team. 2024. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienne, Austria. <<https://www.R-project.org/>>.

Safner T., Gračanin A., Gligora I., Pokorny B., Flajšman K., Apollonio M., Šprem N. 2021 State border fences as a threat to habitat connectivity: a case study from South-Eastern Europe. *Šumarski list* 145: 269-278. <https://doi.org/10.31298/sl.145.5-6.6>

Selva N., Nowak K., Stachowicz I., Kudrenko S. *In press*. Wildlife research and conservation in human conflict-affected areas. In *War Impacts on the Environment*, Pereira P. & Barcelo D. (Eds.). Springer.

Sennett C., Chambers C.L., 2025. International border fences and walls negatively affect wildlife: A review. *Biological Conservation* 302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2024.110957>.

Schmidt K., Kowalczyk R., Kołodziej-Sobocińska M., Niedziałkowska M., Tokarska M., Żmihorski M., Nowak K. 2024. Oddziaływanie zapory granicznej na granicy polsko-białoruskiej na Obiekt Światowego Dziedzictwa "Białowieża Forest". Available: <https://ios.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/ekspertyza-oddziaływanie-zapory-granicznej.pdf>

Su H., Qu L.J., He K. *et al.* 2003. The Great Wall of China: a physical barrier to gene flow?. *Heredity* 90: 212–219. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.hdy.6800237>

Thornton D. H., Wirsing A. J., Lopez-Gonzalez C., Squires J. R., Fisher S., Larsen K. W., Peatt A., Scraftford M. A., Moen R. A., Scully A. E., King T. W., Murray D. L. 2018. Asymmetric cross-border protection of peripheral transboundary species. *Conservation Letters* 11(3): e12430. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12430>

Titley M.A., Butchart S.H.M., Jones V.R., Willis S.G. 2021. Global inequities and political borders challenge nature conservation under climate change. *PNAS* 118(7): e2011204118.

UNESCO. 2024. Report of the joint WHC/IUCN reactive monitoring mission to Białowieża Forest (Belarus/Poland), 18-27 March 2024. Available at: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/documents/207619>

Wade L. 2017. Mexican scientists feel the Trump effect. *Science* 355: 440–441. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.355.6324.440>.

Wajrak A. 2024. Wajrak o Tarczy Wschód nad Bugiem: Wkrótce nie będzie w Polsce czego bronić. 11.12.2024 *Gazeta Wyborcza* URL: <https://wyborcza.pl/7,177851,31535371,wajrak-o-tarczy-wschod-nad-bugiem-wkrotce-nie-bedzie-w-polsce.html#S.MT-K.C-B.2-L.1.duzy>

Xu W., Dejid N., Herrmann V., Sawyer H., Middleton A.D. 2021. Barrier behaviour analysis (BaBa) reveals extensive effects of fencing on wide-ranging ungulates. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 58: 690–698. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13806>

Zhang T., Gibson L. Ma J., Sreekar R., Lindenmayer D., Liu J. 2025. Global patterns of border protected areas reveal gaps in transboundary conservation efforts. *One Earth* 101206.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2025.101206>

Other useful references:

Beyer HL, Gurarie E, Börger L, Panzacchi M, Basille M, Herfindal I, et al. 2016. 'You shall not pass!': quantifying barrier permeability and proximity avoidance by animals. *J Anim Ecol.* 85: 45–53.

de Jonge M.M.J., Gallego-Zamorano J., Huijbregts M.A.J., Schipper A.M., Benítez-López A. 2022. The impacts of linear infrastructure on terrestrial vertebrate populations: A trait-based approach. *Glob Chang Biol.* 28: 7217-723.

Delgado J.D., Arroyo N.L., Arevalo J.R., Fernandez-Palacios J.M. 2007. Edge effects of roads on temperature, light, canopy cover, and canopy height in laurel and pine forests (Tenerife, Canary Islands). *Landscape and Urban Planning* 81: 328-340.

Jones P.F., Jakes A.F., Vegter S.E. et al. 2022. Is it the road or the fence? Influence of linear anthropogenic features on the movement and distribution of a partially migratory ungulate. *Mov Ecol* 10: 37.

Vanak A.T., Thaker M., Slotow R. 2010. Do fences create an edge-effect on the movement patterns of a highly mobile mega-herbivore? *Biological Conservation* 143: 2631-2637.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2010.07.005>

Appendices

Appendix I Information about four borderland areas compiled during a workshop conducted in September 2023.

Table 1. Comparison of four border areas with border infrastructure, either past (Czechia-Germany), present (US-Mexico, Poland-Belarus), or in the process of removal (Slovenia-Croatia).

	Slovenia-Croatia	Czechia-Germany	US-Mexico	Poland-Belarus
Fence types	1) razor wire 2) solid panel mesh	barbed wire with voltage	state by state (variation)	provisional razor wire; concrete, steel & razor wire
Years of fence	2015-2023	1952-1990		2022-present
Length (km)	199	>1000	737 (under Trump)	187
Height (m)	1) razor wire <1m; 2) mesh 4m	max 4m (with some sections higher with spiral)	up to 10m (check)	5.5m (0.5m is razor wire)
Added fortification	one or the other	voltage, minefields, lights, trained dogs; double fence	floodlights	razor wire along ground and elsewhere, electronic barrier, helicopters, outposts
Gaps	frequent (decision to leave parts open; purposeful openings; terrain)	no gaps (fences inland)	haphazard / random gaps	terrain (for now)-wetlands; gates (remain closed)
Stakeholders who provide data / information	hunters, scientists	national park staff (present); at time of fence maybe foresters	communities, NGOs, cattle ranchers	scientists, activists, communities, border guard, media
Stakeholders with stake in the fence	local politicians, farmers, tourists, public	local communities (present) recreation e.g. skiing; foresters (use former military roads for access)	border communities	
Protection / legislation	Natura2000	national park; Natura2000; landscape protection area	biosphere reserve; wildlife refuges; TBC	UNESCO; Natura2000; national park; reserves
Transboundary	\	NP MoU Sumava-Bavarian Forest (present)	Trilateral Agreement (Canada, USA, MX)	UNESCO (1992)

Most vulnerable species (direct)	red deer, roe deer	red deer, capercaillie	low-flying butterflies	red deer
Most vulnerable species (indirect)	red deer, carnivores		Mexican grey wolf	lynx, moose, brown bear, wolves
Confirmed crossings/permeability	wild boar, brown bear, roe deer, red deer, brown hare		black bear	red fox, marten, raccoon dog, domestic cats, other small mammals
Ecological effects	flooding	water regime, light pollution	water regime, light pollution	fragmentation, erosion, connectivity loss, colonization by non-forest plant spp.
Most vulnerable habitats		wetlands, rivers		
Restrictions or limitations on access	farmers' access to agricultural land (needed to make call to police for gate opening); no restrictions in forest; closure of transnational roads	2 km strictly closed / prohibition zone (army only; 12 km border zone (e.g. foresters, geologists with permits)		200-m (10 mo); 15-m ("always"); PL citizens may go into BY (without visa), BY citizens also crossing border (with visa); research denied
Access category	medium-high access	no access	medium-high access	low access
Cross-border relations	positive			family relations; cheaper goods such as gasoline in BY; shared projects especially national park (prior to barrier); provocations by BY army (e.g. helicopters, shooting crossbow at Polish border guard)
Efficacy of intended purpose				there are still crossings
External border	no	not anymore	yes	yes
Fence-related data	ungulate mortality (& injury)	red deer avoidance; vegetation change	species presence	/

Before data	telemetry & genetics (large carnivores); hunting bags (for game spp.); genetics (ungulate spp.)	historical photos; old forest maps (forest type)		telemetry (lynx, bison, wolf, red deer, boar); camera traps; imagery (e.g. high usage cross border animal paths from before barrier?); inventory of invasive nonnative spp.; genetics
After data	telemetry & genetics (large carnivores); hunting bags (for game spp.)	telemetry, vegetation mapping, aerial photos, Lidar		roadkills, tree damage (during construction); camera traps
How state barrier differs from other barriers/fences in respective country	razor wire (material); effects	barbed wire (material); voltage (target was people)		material, height, length, traffic intensity
Restoration efforts	fence removal	fence removal; road remediation with PCBs; volunteers, machines- water regime (focus of restoration)		
Mitigation efforts	chemical repellents used by hunters to reduce fence-related mortality		new gaps	26 animal gates, small animal holes in foundation
Current connectivity	recent reinforcement of lynx is contributing to transboundary population level; GPS data; genetics			depends on spp.
Associated/indirect threats that may add to cumulative effects	altered human activity	herbicides; change in water regime; construction material; tar		vehicle traffic along forest roads; expansion of residential zone; anthropogenic noise; construction material

Benefits	ASF prevention	low human activity		lower hunting pressure (benefit or cost or both?); ASF (?); linear corridor for flying mammals (?)
Tested methods	citizen scientists (hunters, wildlife observers), snow tracks, least cost paths/habitat suitability, genetics; LISIAK database software & app (for citizen science); telemetry	historical data and records; cooperation with hunters (post Iron Curtain era)	drone, GoogleMaps, camera traps	roadkills, tree damages, appearance of non-native plant spp.; telemetry; camera traps; surveys/questionnaires
Planned methods	citizen scientists (hunters, wildlife observers), snow tracks, least cost paths/habitat suitability, species genetics, eDNALISIAK database software & app (for citizen science); telemetry			snow tracking (to be done); high resolution satellite imagery; use of freely available medium resolution imagery to examine land surface temperature differences
Failed methods				did not detect vegetation change / tree loss in 2022 from low res imagery; denied access to video footage from border guard
Not possible methods				insect activity near the fence (15 m restriction); hair traps (15 m)
Analytical methods (highlighting)	Circuitscape; habitat patch connectivity; least cost paths	Image analysis; GIS analysis		CT data: activity, frequency modeling; audio
Funding sources	Horizon, Weave, Life, Interreg	Interreg, Life		NAWA, Life
Outreach & Advocacy	interactions with media		interactions with media	interactions with media

Related Publications by NAWA team members	Pokorny et al. 2017 Safner et al. 2021	Krenova & Nowak 2025	Chambers et al. 2022 Harrity et al. 2024	Jaroszewicz et al. 2021 Nowak et al. 2023 Selva et al. in press Nowak et al. 2024
--	---	----------------------	---	--

Appendix II Images of Eurasian lynx captured by camera traps deployed in this study. The first photo (one in a series of two) is from one of our road sites (500m from Zwierzyniecka Road), and the second image (one in a series of three) is from one of our border sites (250m from the state border in Rezerwat Lasy Naturalne).

